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Cloud for Data-Driven Policy Management

CLOUD FOR DATA-DRIVEN POLICY MANAGEMENT

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Abstract: A description of the software demonstration for the components of the Integrated Data Acquisition and Analytics (DAA) Layer, which provides the analytical capabilities of the PolicyCLOUD platform, including the API Gateway / orchestrator and the built-in analytical tools.

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation/Acronym	Definition
API	Application Programming Interface
DAA	Data Acquisition and Analytics
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
GTD	Global Terrorism Database
ML	Machine Learning
NER	Named Entity Recognition
NLP	Natural Language Processing
PDT	Policy Development Toolkit
POS	Part-of-Speech
REST	Representational State Transfer
SKA	Situational Knowledge Acquisition

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Executive Summary

This document is the second software demonstrator deliverable of PolicyCLOUD at M22 (October 2021) of the project and is intended for the reviewers of the software deliverables.

This deliverable provides a second and much upgraded description of the software demonstration for the components of the Integrated Data Acquisition and Analytics (DAA) Layer, which provides the analytical capabilities of the PolicyCLOUD platform. The components include the DAA API Gateway (responsible for the overall orchestration and the layer API), the built-in analytical tools - for Data cleaning and interoperability, Situational Knowledge, Opinion Mining & Sentiment Analysis and Social Dynamics & Behavioural Data analysis, and the Operational Data Repository.

The DAA API Gateway (responsible for the overall orchestration and the layer API) as well as the built-in analytical tools for Data cleaning and interoperability, Situational Knowledge, Opinion Mining & Sentiment Analysis have been integrated with almost all the use cases at least in standalone mode. In addition, full integration for two use cases was demonstrated during the review of June 2021.

The advanced Social Dynamics & Behavioural Data analysis component is fully operational in standalone mode and will be integrated with the PolicyCLOUD framework this coming year.

In terms of used infrastructure, the Operational Data Repository has been enhanced thanks to the adoption of the “seamless” technology (section 4.4 of [34]) which offers a two-tier storage architecture based on the LeanXcale relational database: the first tier which was used till now and the Object Storage: the second tier. This novel architecture presents single logical datasets to users which can be explored with SQL.

1. Introduction

1.1 Data Acquisition and Analytics Layer

The Data Acquisition and Analytics (DAA) layer is designed for extensibility and reusability of analytic functions. New analytics functions can be registered into PolicyCLOUD and reused for applying analytics on new and existing registered data sources. The detailed architecture and functionality are provided in D4.3 `Reusable Model & Analytical Tools: Design and Open Specification 2` [34]. Figure 1 provides the high-level architecture of the DAA layer displaying the main components and the interactions with the various exploiters.

FIGURE 1 - DATA ACQUISITION AND ANALYTICS LAYER

The design is based on the serverless model, and more specifically on the open-source project Apache OpenWhisk [8]: a distributed serverless platform, where functions are activated on demand, either directly through a PolicyCLOUD user request or by event/rule.

We differentiate between two main types of functions:

1. Analytic-ingest function, used to apply initial analytic and/or transformation on the data fusion path of data sources.
2. Analytic function, triggered by the PolicyCLOUD users through the Policy Layer. These functions perform an analysis on an (already ingested) specified data source to provide analytic insights needed for policy decisions.

The DAA API Gateway component provides the external frontend of the DAA layer, as well as all required orchestration for the function and data source registrations and activation of the API. The other components are the built-in analytics functions for Data Cleaning and Interoperability, Situational Knowledge, Opinion Mining & Sentiment Analysis, and the Operational Data Repository component which is provided by the LeanXcale database. All these components (as well as the OpenWhisk cluster and the LeanXcale database) are running above a Kubernetes cluster. The Social Dynamics & Behavioural Data analysis component is running in standalone mode and will be able to communicate with the PolicyCLOUD data store.

1.2 Summary of Changes: DAA Layer

Each of the components of the DAA layer has its summary of changes subsection. Therefore, in this summary we will only mention:

The addition of the logging service and container registry (see 2.2.2).

Also, the Cloud Gateway (which pertains to WP3) and for which the Twitter API has been integrated, thus enabling real streaming datasets.

As a global aspect, the DAA layer has been stable from the issuance of the PolicyCLOUD. D4.2 Reusable Model & Analytical Tools: Software Prototype 1 [36], however in this second version of the demonstrator, all components are now integrated, and two use cases are running end to end on the testbed infrastructure. Furthermore, integration work has been performed for the Sofia and London use cases, which are now close to being integrated with the DAA layer.

2. Prototype overview

A standalone prototype comprising all the components with initial two end-to-end scenario demonstrations were performed during the review of June 2021. They demonstrated integrations of the developed software components where the data was streamed from the Gateway to the data storage through Apache Kafka and where the analytic-ingest functions were run over the Apache OpenWhisk framework.

Additional scenarios are being worked on and many analytic components are now applied to additional scenarios. The end-to-end integration and demonstration for these additional scenarios will be delivered in the third software demonstrator.

The advanced analytic capabilities of the “Politika” software will be provided in a stand-alone module capable of sending and receiving datasets from the rest of the PolicyCLOUD platform. This capability will be demonstrated in the last version of this deliverable: D4.6 Reusable Model & Analytical Tools: Software Prototype 3, due in October 2022.

Figure 2 depicts the terrorist heatmap use case running in DAA. Once the dataset has been ingested, Heatmap analytic functions may be commanded to be applied on the dataset through the Policy Development Toolkit (PDT):

FIGURE 2 - GTD USECASE

Figure 3 shows the SARGA use case, which uses a streaming dataset.

FIGURE 3 - SARGA USECASE

2.1 Main components of the prototype

This section provides the description of the components included in the prototype.

2.1.1 DAA API Gateway

The DAA API Gateway developed in Task 4.1 is responsible for the orchestration and integration of all the components of the DAA layer (analytic functions, data sources, data repository) as well as providing the external interface for the layer's exploiters – analytic owners, data source owners, and the Policy layer (through which the end user apply desired analytics). Its roles include forming the proper setup of the registered analytic functions and data sources to ensure the correct data ingest process (applying the required ingest-time analytics/transformation – in both Ingest-now and Streaming modes), and applying the requested analytics on the requested data source. The DAA API Gateway is implemented as a set of serverless functions (in the OpenWhisk cluster), where the state is managed both on the OpenWhisk itself (e.g., analytic functions' metadata) and the database.

2.1.2 Enhanced Interoperability & Data Cleaning

2.1.2.1 DATA CLEANING COMPONENT

The scope of the Data Cleaning component is to undertake all the processes regarding the data validation and data cleaning of all the incoming heterogeneous data, to the possible extent. The Data Cleaning component provides the interface that implements the data cleaning workflow as documented in deliverables D4.1 [1] and then D4.3 [34], in order to be utilized by the rest of the PolicyCLOUD components, ensuring data accuracy and consistency of the incoming datasets.

The updated architecture and design of the Data Cleaning component was documented in D4.3 with the purpose of addressing the volatility of the incoming data information to improve data accuracy, consistency and completeness for the PolicyCLOUD platform. Thus, the Data Cleaning component implements all the processes that identify datasets that may contain inaccurate, incorrect, incomplete or irrelevant data elements and consequently replace, modify or delete these data elements safeguarding

the reliability and appropriateness of the incoming data information. The software prototype of the Data Cleaning component was driven by this specification.

In this context, the Data Cleaning component is composed of one (1) main service, namely the `DataCleaningService`, which in turn consists of three (3) internal services: the `ValidationService`, the `CleaningService`, and the `VerificationService`. The main service, `DataCleaningService`, handles all the incoming and outgoing traffic of the DataCleaner component and is the only service exposed to the rest of the platform components. Contrary to the main service, the three (3) internal services are not exposed to the rest of the platform components, whereas the `DataCleaningService` is interacting with these services internally so as to realize the data cleaning workflow. The provided functionalities of the services are further depicted below.

- **DataCleaningService:** the main service of the Data Cleaning component in charge of executing the data cleaning workflow of PolicyCLOUD platform. Since the data cleaning workflow comprises several sequential steps, each one implemented by one of the internal services of the component, the `DataCleaningService` is responsible for the orchestration of these internal services as well as for monitoring their execution, and thus providing the execution results to the requestor. In addition to the data cleaning workflow execution, the `DataCleaningService` is responsible for the implementation of the single interface for data cleaning requests. In deeper detail, the `DataCleaningService` implements one (1) main function:
 - *initiateCleaning (dataset: File): Void:* This is the main function that initiates the `DataCleaningService`. It receives as input the provided dataset. This dataset is either already stored or still streaming and is in json format. It is responsible for orchestrating the rest of the internal services towards the execution of the data cleaning workflow.
- **ValidationService:** the internal service responsible for the data validation processing of the incoming data. The `ValidationService` performs a series of validation checks in order to evaluate the conformance to a set of constraints currently integrated in the business logic of the service. The current list of validation rules includes the following (with regards to the historical data):
 - Conformance to specific data type.
 - Conformance to mandatory fields.
 - Conformance to specific value length.
 - Conformance to specific value representation.
 - Conformance to specific value range.
 - Identification of duplicate values for the data elements.
 - Identification of duplicate data elements.

It should be noted that the list of the validation rules will be furtherly enriched as the project evolves.

As for its provided functions, the `ValidationService` implements the following functions:

- *validateData(dataset: File): List:* This is the main function that initiates the `ValidationService`. It receives as an input the provided dataset (in json format), being responsible for identifying and returning the list of errors based on the evaluation of the set of the constraints that have been set. In order to properly work, `validateData` exploits the following internal functions:

- *checkString(i: String): Boolean*: This is an internal function validating the conformance to the specific data type.
- *checkDecimal(d: Decimal): Boolean*: This is an internal function validating the conformance to the specific data type.
- *checkInt(i: Integer): Boolean*: This is an internal function validating the conformance to the specific data type.
- *checkMaxDigits(i: Numerical): Boolean*: This is an internal function validating the conformance to the specific value length.
- *checkRange(i: Numerical, j: Numerical): Boolean*: This is an internal function validating the conformance to the specific value range.

Based on the aforementioned, Figure 4 depicts a snapshot of an uploaded dataset containing historical data, prior to performing any cleaning action. It should be mentioned that for this dataset, a data schema has been already created including all the validation rules that each row and column of the dataset should obey to. What is more, it should be noted that this dataset refers to the scenario that regards the Participatory Policies Against Radicalization (Scenario #1.1), as it is documented in D2.2 [2].

eventid	year	imonth	iday	approxdateextended	resolutio	country	country_t	region	region_txt	provstate	city	latitude	longitude	specificity	vicinity	location	summary
1.97E+11	1970	1	14	0		217	United St	1	North America	Illinois	Champaig	40,11675	-88,2393	1	0	Champaig	1/14/1970
1.97E+11	1970	1	15	0		218	Uruguay	3	South America	Montevid	Montevid	-34,8912	-56,1872	1	0		
1.97E+11	1970	1	19	0		217	United St	1	North America	Washingt	Seattle	47,61079	-122,331	1	0	Seattle Ur	1/17/1970

FIGURE 4 - SNAPSHOT OF GTD DATA

Similarly, Figure 5 depicts a snapshot of retrieved streaming Twitter data, prior to performing any cleaning action. It should be mentioned that this data refers to the scenario that regards the Intelligent Policies for The Denomination of Origin (Scenario #2.1), as documented in D2.6.

La derrota del pasado domingo contra el Barbastro ya es historia. Nuestros jugadores ya están de pie, nuestro equipo ya se ha puesto el mono de faena para resarcirse de ese traspiés. <https://t.co/Nn16g9p97e>

FIGURE 5 - SNAPSHOT OF TWITTER DATA

- **CleaningService**: It is the internal service responsible for the cleaning of the incoming data. The CleaningService eliminates the list of errors identified by the ValidationService by applying all the necessary corrective actions on the data elements marked with errors. Cleaning is performed automatically based on a set of actions currently integrated in the business logic of the component. The current list of possible cleaning actions includes the following:

For stored data:

- Deletion (drop) of the complete record (row).
- Replacement of data element's value with the mean value.
- Replacement of data element's value with the maximum value.
- Replacement of data element's value with the minimum value.

- Replacement of data element's value with the most frequent value.

For streaming data:

- Use of NLP processes.

It should be noted that the list of the cleaning actions will be furtherly enriched as the project evolves.

The CleaningService implements the following functions:

- *cleanHistoricalData(errors: List, dataset: File): File*: This is the main function that initiates the CleaningService when receiving historical data. It receives as an input the provided dataset (in json format), as well as the identified list of errors produced by the ValidationService, being responsible for constructing and returning the cleaned dataset. In order to properly work, cleanHistoricalData exploits the following internal functions:
 - *dropRow(row_num: Integer): Void*: This is an internal function rejecting the complete record (row).
 - *replaceWithMean(column: String, row_num: Integer): Void*: This is an internal function replacing the data element's value with the mean value.
 - *replaceWithMax(column: String, row_num: Integer): Void*: This is an internal function replacing the data element's value with the maximum value.
 - *replaceWithMinimum(column: String, row_num: Integer): Void*: This is an internal function replacing the data element's value with the minimum value.
 - *replaceWithMostFrequent(column: String, row_num: Integer): Void*: This is an internal function replacing the data element's value with the most frequent value.
- *cleanStreamingData(dataset: File): File*: is the main function that initiates the CleaningService when receiving streaming data. It receives as an input the provided data (in json format), responsible for constructing and returning the cleaned dataset. In order to properly work, cleanStreamingData exploits the following internal functions:
 - *removeEmojis(twitter_text: String): String*: an internal function which removes any emojis that exist in the data.
 - *removeStopwords(twitter_text: String): String*: an internal function which removes any stopwords that exist in the data.
 - *removePunctuations(twitter_text: String): String*: an internal function which removes any punctuations that exist in the data.
 - *removeMention(twitter_text: String): String*: an internal function which removes any mentions that exist in the data.
 - *removeHashtag(twitter_text: String): String*: an internal function which removes any hashtags that exist in the data.

Based on the aforementioned, in the provided example of the historical data (GTD), the row with the identified error (null value) has been dropped (Figure 6). This was requested by the cleaning actions of the specific Scenario, where it was described that in the case that a null value would appear, then the overall row containing this null value should be deleted.

eventid	year	imonth	iday	approxdate	extended	resolution	country	country_t	region	region_txt	provstate	city	latitude	longitude	specificity	vicinity	location	summary
1,97E+11	1970	1	14			0	217	United Stc	1	North America	Illinois	Champaig	40,11675	-88,2393	1	0	Champaig	1/14/1970
1,97E+11	1970	1	19			0	217	United Stc	1	North America	Washingt	Seattle	47,61079	-122,331	1	0	Seattle Ur	1/17/1970

FIGURE 6 - SNAPSHOT OF THE CLEANED DATASET

With regards to the collected streaming (Twitter) data, all the needed cleaning corrections were applied, removing in this case all the emojis, stopwords, punctuations, mentions, and tags that existed in the ingested data (Figure 7).

```
CF Illueca CD Cariñena Estadio " Papa Luna " 17 00 horas Domingo 10 octubre La derrota pasado domingo Barbastro historia Nue-
tros jugadores pie equipo puesto mono faena resarcirse traspiés
```

FIGURE 7 - SNAPSHOT OF THE CLEANED DATASET

- **VerificationService:** is the internal service responsible for the verification and evaluation of the corrective actions undertaken by the CleaningService, aiming at ensuring the accuracy and the consistency of the updated incoming data according to the PolicyCLOUD platform requirements. In more detail, the VerificationService implements the following main function:
 - *verifyData(): List:* the main function that initiates the VerificationService. It receives as input the provided dataset (in json format), the cleaned dataset (in json format), as well as the identified list of errors, being responsible for the final verification and evaluation of the corrective actions in combination with the actual cleaned dataset, and thus outputting the results of the evaluation. In case that no corrective action is needed, a null list is returned. Otherwise, the VerificationService returns a list of additional corrective actions that should be done once or repetitively by the CleaningService.

Based on the aforementioned, in the two (2) provided examples, the VerificationService checks and confirms that the CleaningService has successfully performed all the required cleaning actions, returning a null List since no further corrective actions are needed to take place.

2.1.2.2 ENHANCED INTEROPERABILITY COMPONENT

Under the scope of this Deliverable, the 2nd Software Prototype of Enhanced Interoperability component consists of several sub-tasks, which are further separated into different layers of the overall proposed pipeline which also introduced in the D4.3 Reusable Model & Analytical Tools Design and Open Specification 2 [34]. The initial design of these layers, which integrate Semantic Web technologies with Natural Language Processing (NLP) technologies and tasks, includes complete workflows and pipelines for annotating cleaned data, which are being sent into the Enhanced Interoperability Component from the Data Cleaning Component. Moreover, as also introduced in the D4.3 through these coupled technologies and methods, the Enhanced Interoperability Component seeks to provide a state-of-the-art approach to achieve interoperability in the data-driven policy making domain. Introduced in D4.3, SemAI entitles this proposed hybrid approach and is a combination of commonly used semantic techniques coupled with the utilization of NLP tasks and methods. The latter is being implemented and used from the early beginning steps of the Enhanced Interoperability Component. To this end, the main functionality of the first sub-component of the Enhanced Interoperability component, that is introduced under the scope of this 2nd Software Prototype, is to annotate cleaned data with URIs pointing to

corresponding Wikidata and DBpedia [4] entities & proper Ontologies, by utilizing SemAI techniques. On top of this, the final extraction of this sub-component is URI annotated data in JSON format. To this end, the system will be able to automatically integrate data from different sources by replacing the context-dependent keys in the JSON output with URIs pointing to semantic vocabularies that will be used to represent and link the data [5].

Furthermore, as analysed in D4.3 after fetching cleaned data from the Data Cleaning Component, the Enhanced Interoperability Component seeks to implement the hybrid approach of SemAI through two core subtasks/sub-components: the Linguistic & Semantic Analysis with NLP (1st sub-component) and the Ontology Mapping (2nd sub-component).

To exploit what the SemAI offers, data has first to be structured and annotated. To this end, in the first sub-component presented and introduced in this Deliverable, cleaned data will be analyzed, transformed and annotated with appropriate URI metadata through the use of Semantic Web technologies and NLP tasks, such as Named Entity Recognition (NER), Part-of-Speech Tagging (POS Tagging) and Named Entity Linking (NEL). These coupled functionalities are being used into three different layers/steps of the overall sub-component as introduced below. Moreover, semantic and syntactic URI annotated data are interlinked through the Ontology Mapping task. The overall Interoperability component is further enhanced and completed by the Ontology Mapping mechanism, where a Topic Detection and Annotation sub-component detects the topic of the given data and afterwards an Ontology Mapping and structuring mechanism are used in order to interlink not only URI annotated data with proper ontologies, but also to interlink and correlate datasets among them.

On top of this, more concrete examples and details are given below for some of the core functionalities/services that are implemented under the scope of these two sub-components. To this end, below are the outcomes of some core sub-tasks for these two sub-components. In the scope of the below demonstration tweets for the SARGA Use Case that were fetched from the Cloud Gateways and APIs component of the PolicyCLOUD project were processed.

- **POS Tagging:** POS tagging task is used after Tokenization and sentence splitting tasks. The part-of-speech tagger is responsible to assign to each token an extended POS tag and to identify its role and usage in the text. Following is an example of the outcome of the POS tagging task that was implemented on a raw sentence.

```
[(x.orth_,x.pos_, x.lemma_) for x in [y
                                     for y
                                     in nlp_es(str(article_spanish))
                                     if not y.is_stop and y.pos_ != 'PUNCT']]

('Cariñena', 'PROPN', 'Cariñena'),
('8', 'NUM', '8'),
('0', 'NUM', '0'),
('1', 'NUM', '1'),
('Edición', 'PROPN', 'Edición'),
('limitada', 'ADJ', 'limitar'),
('c', 'PROPN', 'c'),
('Souvignon', 'PROPN', 'Souvignon'),
('2014', 'NUM', '2014'),
('Merlot', 'PROPN', 'Merlot'),
('2015', 'NUM', '2015'),
('Syrah', 'PROPN', 'Syrah'),
('2016', 'NUM', '2016'),
('empujar', 'VERB', 'empujar'),
('migas', 'NOUN', 'migar'),
('calcando', 'VERB', 'calcar'),
('fresco', 'ADJ', 'fresco'),
('hoyRT', 'PROPN', 'hoyRT'),
...]
```

```
[(x.orth_,x.pos_, x.lemma_) for x in [y
                                     for y
                                     in nlp_en(str(article_english))
                                     if not y.is_stop and y.pos_ != 'PUNCT']]

[('', 'VERB', ''),
 ('s', 'VERB', 's'),
 ('winewednesday', 'PROPN', 'winewednesday'),
 ('calls', 'VERB', 'call'),
 ('bottle', 'NOUN', 'bottle'),
 ('2017', 'NUM', '2017'),
 ('Embruix', 'PROPN', 'Embruix'),
 ('Vall', 'PROPN', 'Vall'),
 ('Llach', 'PROPN', 'Llach'),
 ('Garnacha', 'PROPN', 'Garnacha'),
 ('Merlot', 'PROPN', 'Merlot'),
 ('Syrah', 'PROPN', 'Syrah'),
 ('Cariñena', 'PROPN', 'Cariñena'),
 ('Cabernet', 'PROPN', 'Cabernet'),
 ('Sauvignon', 'PROPN', 'Sauvignon'),
 ('Priorat', 'PROPN', 'Priorat'),
 ('Spain', 'PROPN', 'Spain'),
```

FIGURE 8 - POS TAGGING

- NER Task:** Named Entity Recognition (NER) task is the process of classifying named entities found in a text into predefined categories, such as persons, places, organizations, dates, etc. To this end, spaCy and its built-in functions are being utilized. In addition, this specific NLP subtask is being utilized for both the English and Spanish languages, hence the respective NLP pipelines provided by spaCy are being used for these specific languages. More specifically, for the English language the *en_core_web_sm* package has been downloaded and used, which is one of spaCy's English tokenizers, taggers, parsers and NER pipelines and tools. In addition, concerning the Spanish language the *es_core_news_md* pipeline has been downloaded and used, which is the respective version of spaCy's NLP pipelines for the Spanish language. On top of this, spaCy uses a statistical model to classify a broad range of entities, including persons, events, locations, dates, cardinals, nationalities / religions among other entities. Moreover, *displacy* has been used in order to visualize the outcomes of this subtask, as it is spaCy's built-in named entity visualizer that allows checking the model's predictions. Following is an example of the NER task implemented on raw text.


```
{'text': 'La recaudación obtenida en la venta de esta edición limitada a 500 botellas será en beneficio de la Asociación Cultural Joaquín Carbonell\n\nhttps://t.co/wPURQq8EkA en @periodicoaragon',
  'labels':
  [
    {125, 128, 'CARDINAL', 'http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q23610', '500'}
  ]
}
]
[
  {'text': 'For the whole month of October try a glass of 2019 La Cappuccina Soave for $8 or a bottle for $24, or try a bottle of 2017 Embrui de Vall Llach [Garnacha, Merlot, Syrah, Cariñena, Cabernet Sauvignon] for only $60!',
  'labels': [
    {46, 50, 'DATE', 'http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q25274', '2019'},
    {76, 77, 'NUMBER', 'http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q23348', '8'},
    {95, 97, 'MONEY', 'http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q23857', '24'},
    {118, 122, 'DATE', 'http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q25290', '2017'},
    {156, 162, 'ORG', 'http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q213338', 'Merlot'},
    {164, 169, 'PERSON', 'http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q332720', 'Syrah'},
    {171, 179, 'ORG', 'http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q984529', 'Cariñena'}
  ]
},
  {'text': 'Book your reservation below! \n\n',
  'labels': []
},
  {'text': 'https://t.co/DXUMdgHdIH https://t.co/wl2UILxJee',
  'labels': []
}
]
```

- Topic Identification:** Alongside the semantic annotation of the data, the SemAI hybrid mechanism provides a topic annotation to the original dataset. The latter is achieved by using subtask of Topic Identification or Topic Modelling. To this end, the component introduces a solution of dataset interoperability in order to better identify interlinking and correlations between different datasets. For this specific subtask three (3) different models were utilized in order to identify the most appropriate topic identification algorithm for the SARGA use case as implemented in corresponding tweets under the scope of this specific scenario. More specifically, these three (3) topics modelling algorithms were the Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) [39], the Latent semantic analysis (LSA) [40], and the Hierarchical Dirichlet Process (HDP) [41]. For selecting and evaluating these models, the topic coherence coefficient was selected as a comparison measure [42]. In general, good topics are considered topics that can be described by a short label, therefore this is what the topic coherence measure should capture, so the best models achieve highest topic coherence scores.

FIGURE 11 - TOPIC MODELS COHERENCES

Figure 11 shows that the HDP model provides the best definition and identification as it has the highest coherence among the three (3) examined models. Hence, the topics of this model will be selected as the final topics with which the corresponding dataset will be tagged and annotated.

- Ontology Mapping:** The approach being followed in the Ontology Mapping subtask is to utilize a Python driver that initializes the connection with the Neo4j graph database. Neo4j has been selected as it is a native graph database, built from the ground up to leverage not only data but also data semantic and syntactic relationships. To this end, the SemAI mechanism will be able to store all the cleaned tweet text to Neo4j. Having already performed the entity extraction, entity linking and the topic identification algorithms on the text of each tweet, it is then feasible for the system to save the tweet text, tweet id, and all the extracted entities to a JSON file that can then be used to save and update the Neo4j graph, and to extend the data model through the connection and interlinking of the Tweet nodes with new Entities, such as Persons, Locations, and Organizations, as also to newly created Topic nodes as identified by the previous subtasks of NER and Topic Identification.

2.1.2.3 SUMMARY OF CHANGES: ENHANCED INTEROPERABILITY AND DATA CLEANING

In this Deliverable and on contrary to D4.2, the updated architecture of the Data Cleaning component has been applied and validated in both stored data and streaming (Twitter) data, verifying the successful applicability of the Data Cleaning component in both cases. Furthermore, the Data Cleaning component has been redesigned and implemented in a more dynamic way so that its execution only requires data and no longer the corresponding data schemas defined by the Use Case partners. In the updated version of the component, the data schema is automatically created by the developed mechanism, and then used for the cleaning process.

With regards to Enhanced Interoperability, the overall workflow of the Enhanced Interoperability component is being utilized and introduced. More specifically, in this deliverable are being presented all the steps and sub-tasks of the SemAI hybrid mechanism which incorporates the functionalities and the

scopes of the Enhanced Interoperability component, and which is further divided into two (2) integrated sub-components as analyzed above, the Semantic and Syntactic Analysis sub-component and the Ontology Mapping sub-component. Furthermore, the implementation and the demonstration of the 1st Software prototype of the Enhanced Interoperability component was conducted on dummy data in the context of D4.2. In contrast to the above, in this specific deliverable all the sub-tasks of the component have been implemented and are being demonstrated with actual data from the Use Case 2.1.3 Scenario C as described in D6.3 Use Case Scenarios Definition & Design [3].

In addition, in Section 2.2 the endpoint with which one can trigger the overall functionalities and mechanism presented above is being presented. In D4.2 the Enhanced Interoperability component was only provided through an iPython Notebook. On top of this, the Topic Identification mechanism is introduced and analyzed in this deliverable. Also, the final subtask of the SemAI hybrid mechanism, the Ontology Mapping, and its outcomes are also presented. Finally, this 2nd Software Prototype of the Enhanced Interoperability component has been utilized and supports data either in English or in Spanish, in order to provide a - as much as possible - a language independent solution. More specifically, the current approach followed for the implementation of the SemAI mechanism has focused on these two (2) specific languages and the pipelines and workflows that have been implemented take advantage of NLP tools only for these languages. Moreover, concerning the Ontology Mapping subtask various ontologies from different languages should be leveraged in order to create corresponding dictionaries of entities and interlink/map them with the identified entities and topics from the NER and Topic Identification subtasks. The latter is not envisioned so far from the PolicyCLOUD scope and objectives.

Very importantly, contrary to D4.2, both the Enhanced Interoperability and the Data Cleaning components, have now been integrated with OpenWhisk which permits now to stakeholders to trigger and activate these components on demand and dynamically.

2.1.3 Situational Knowledge Acquisition & Analysis

2.1.3.1 DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS CONDUCTED BY DATA VISUALIZATION

In this second release the situational knowledge acquisition and analysis (SKA) task has been focused at providing Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA) with two additional use cases. In particular, in this second release we deliver the SKA-EDA v1 component which addresses the following use cases:

- Use Case 3 (Facilitating urban policy making and monitoring through crowdsourcing data analysis). The EDA is applied to the following scenarios: SC1 - Road Infrastructure, SC2 - Environment and Air Quality, SC3 - Waste Collection and Waste Disposal, SC4 - Transport and Parking, SC5 - Cleanliness of Public Spaces, SC6 - Violation of Public Order.
- Use case 4 (Predictive analysis towards unemployment risks identification and policy making), the EDA is applied to the first scenario "Scenario A: Conduct analysis based on the statistics of specific time periods".

According to (Kabita Sahoo, 2019) [28], exploratory data analysis can be considered as the exploration of the dataset with the aim of getting statistical characteristics of the dataset such as "*measures of central tendency (comprising the mean, the mode and the median), measures of spread (comprising the standard deviation and variance), the shape of the distribution and the existence of outliers*".

In our case, due to the nature of the managed datasets and the scenarios raised for the PolicyCLOUD use cases, this SKA-EDA first prototype is focused on providing exploration of datasets based on descriptive analysis conducted by data visualization. Thus, the SKA-EDA v1 is conceived as an exploratory data analysis tool in charge of collecting datasets, applying some transformations, performing some computations and providing different json results to be plotted in the visualization components (addressed in Work package 6). Nevertheless, some pure EDA-based analysis, such as the shape of distribution for use case 4, will be explored and included into the SKA-EDA v2 for providing the policy maker more statistical parameters about the explored dataset.

In the context of this second prototype, all scenarios for Use Case 3 will use data from Sofia Municipality's Contact Centre CallSofia (mobile application, 24/7 phone contact centre, and web channel). This data is distributed into 6 datasets (one per each of the scenarios SC1, SC2, SC3, SC4, SC5 and SC6) containing incidents/signals in the urban environment of the Sofia city. All datasets have the same schema and will have the same end-to-end KPI and analytical objectives. Dataset (s) comprises 26 variables, out of which 10 of them will be used for the use case (see picture 15 - Use Case 3 structure sample for more details). These 10 variables are categorical variables, therefore the SKA-EDA v1 is focused on assisting the policy maker with the categorical variables distributions, concretely:

- *Variable Distribution/Frequency distribution across one category*, it represents "all the values of the variable along with the frequency of each one" [29]. In particular, the number of incidents of each district and the number of incidents of each subcategory. The results are portrayed as a horizontal bar chart.

- *Geographical Distribution*, containing a list of events/signals that happen in the specific values of the geographical variable. The results are portrayed as a heat map.
- *Variables Distribution/Frequency distribution across several categories*, it represents “all the pairs (value1, value 2) of two variables along with the frequency of each one. In particular, the combination of month-subcategory and subcategory-district. The results are portrayed as a bar charts.

In the case of Use Case 4, SKA-EDA v1 uses the “JSA And UC Claimants In Camden” dataset, a *series counting the number of people claiming Jobseeker's Allowance plus those who claim Universal Credit* [30]. It comprises 10 variables (see Figure 19 - Use Case 4 structure sample for more detail), from which mostly “Value”, “Gender” and the “Date” are used for assisting the policy maker with:

- *Accumulation of one variable across multiple categories*. This distribution does not rely on the frequency distribution across several categories (counting the number of apparitions of a specific(s) value(s)) but in the accumulated value (sum the value of a specific numeric variable) across several categories. In particular, the accumulation of “Value” (number of claimants) across Gender and Year/Month. The results are portrayed as a bar chart.

2.1.3.2 SUMMARY OF CHANGE: SITUATIONAL KNOWLEDGE ACQUISITION & ANALYSIS

This second release is focused on enhancing the exploratory data analysis in the PolicyCLOUD project by:

- enlarging the planned functionality, in the context of exploratory data analysis in PolicyCLOUD, by introducing (categorical) variable distributions: frequency distribution across one (or several) categories and accumulation distribution
- making the EDA analysis general enough to be applied to several use cases/scenarios
- embedding an enhanced version of SKA-HeatMap_v1 (released in the 1 prototype) into SKA-EDA v1
- implementing part of the Use Case 3 scenarios (SC1 - Road Infrastructure, SC2 – Environment and Air Quality, SC3 – Waste Collection and Waste Disposal, SC4 – Transport and Parking, SC5 – Cleanliness of Public Spaces, SC6 – Violation of Public Order) and the first scenario for Use Case 4.
- researching the inclusion of frequency distribution, for those numerical variables, as part of the statistical characteristics provided by SKA_EDA.

2.1.4 Opinion Mining & Sentiment Analysis

For this second release, the functionality provided from this task is a second version of the sentiment analysis core component described and provided in D4.1 [1] and D4.2 [36]. While the previous version was focused on a document-level approach, *“the document contains an opinion on one main object expressed by the author of the document”* [31], this new version will be based on an entity-level sentiment analysis (ELSA) approach [33], [15], [16] in charge of providing *“author sentiment towards various entities in text”* as cited in [32], which can be considered as an intermediate granularity between sentence-level sentiment, *“It’s known that the entity discussed in the sentence and there is just one single opinion in each sentence”* and aspect-level sentiment *“people talk about entities that have many aspects (attributes) and they have a different opinion about each of the aspects”*.

In particular, it will cover the analytical part of the Scenario B from UC#2 (“Intelligent policies for the development of denomination of origin”) which aim to get the positive, negative and neutral opinions about different wine related entities based on social media data.

A Named-entity recognition process will be performed as first steps in the ELSA. This process will help for the entity identification, which then will be scored with polarity, and it will be of the Enhanced Interoperability component following an ontology -based approach.

2.1.4.1 TRADITIONAL MACHINE LEARNING APPROACHES VS DEEP/LEARNING APPROACHES

The term “Sentiment Analysis” was first introduced at the early beginnings of the 21st century [17], using various developed standards to identify the emotion in a text, while the term opinion mining made its first appearance almost at the same time [18].

At its heart, Sentiment Analysis employs various NLP and Machine Learning techniques that are implemented to classify a text based on sentiments. The first attempts were made in the early 21st century where researchers aimed to classify long texts into categories according to the overall feeling they express [19]. Few years ago, an attempt to rank online reviews on cars, movies, banks and travel destinations was conducted using statistical methods and unsupervised learning based on point mutual information (Pointwise Mutual Information (PMI) index) between a phrase containing an adjective or adverb and words “excellent” and “poor” [20]. Furthermore, in the same year, the application of supervised machine learning algorithms, such as Naive Bayes, Maximum Entropy Classification and SVMs, was examined by using various attributes to classify the problem of Sentiment Analysis for movie reviews [21].

Although sentiment analysis is one of the first tasks of NLP for which the research community had remarkable results, the evolution and wide use of Deep Neural Networks over the past years has led to the utilization of Neural Networks in Sentiment Analysis tasks. With the advances in the field of Deep Learning, many new algorithms have flourished with the potential to enhance Sentiment Analysis.

Hence, recent research efforts are oriented towards the use of Neural Networks and Deep Learning (DL) techniques, such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) or Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), which have shown remarkable results, and which indeed can be leveraged for the task of Sentiment Analysis.

Support Vector Machines (SVM) and Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) were compared for document level sentiment classification [22]. This research effort led to the conclusion that ANN can compete with SVMs in most cases. Moreover, a comparison between traditional Machine Learning and Deep Learning Neural Networks indicated that the results produced by Neural Networks were not significantly affected by either balanced or unbalanced data composition conditions, thus the performance of the Deep Learning Neural Network algorithm was overwhelming comparing to the performance of the SVM and Naïve-Bayes, two of most widely used traditional Machine Learning algorithms [23].

On top of this, a CNN variant named BoW-CNN was introduced that employs bag-of-word conversion in the convolution layer [24]. This research resulted in the design of a new model, called Seq-CNN, which keeps the sequential information of words by concatenating the one-hot vector of multiple words.

Moreover, the advent of the Attention Mechanism was one of the most valuable breakthroughs in Deep Learning research [25]. Fields like Natural Language Processing (NLP) and even Computer Vision have been revolutionized by the Attention Mechanism. In this context, a hierarchical attention network for document level sentiment rating prediction of reviews was introduced [26]. The model includes two levels of attention mechanisms: one at the word level and the other at the sentence level, which allows the model to pay more or less attention to individual words or sentences in constructing the representation of a document. In the same context, in a more recent research the superiority of BERT-based models for capturing aspect-based sentiment and their robustness to overfitting was demonstrated [27]. To conclude, Deep learning algorithms in most cases clearly outperform traditional Machine Learning algorithms. However, in some rare cases where the differences in the results of those two approaches are not substantial enough then Machine Learning algorithms should be used as they are easier to implement.

One of the cases that Deep Learning approaches should be used instead of the traditional Machine Learning approaches is the task of Entity-Level Sentiment Analysis (ELSA). The latter aims to identify fine-grained opinion polarity towards specific entities and is a challenging and complex subtask of Sentiment Analysis (SA) due to additional target and entity level information and knowledge extraction that should be achieved from a given text/sentence. The main objective of this task is to classify the sentiments of a text concerning already identified and extracted entities.

Under the scopes of the PolicyCLOUD project the utilization of Deep Learning approaches, such as Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) and Transformers architectures, based on attention-mechanisms [25], has been selected in order to perform the Entity-Level Sentiment Analysis (ELSA) due to the complexity of the overall tasks and pipelines and the lack of training data that are mandatory in the implementation of Machine Learning algorithms.

2.1.4.2 INTEGRATION OF ENTITY-LEVEL SENTIMENT ANALYSIS IN POLICYCLOUD

The ELSA system in Policy Cloud follows a similar approach than the document-based sentiment delivered for release 1. Therefore, it consists of two independent processes:

- **Ingest Function:** This first process is responsible for the entity-based sentiment analysis per se. It generates positive/negative/neutral tags related to the entities. It is meant to be run in streaming mode as an ingest function. Therefore, it takes the data from input Kafka topic(s), executes the microservice component (the core of the component) and outputs into another Kafka topic.
 - **The ELSA microservice:** Is the core process in charge of computing the entity-level sentiment analysis per ser. This analysis, as it has been commented before, is a BERT-based Entity Level Sentiment Analysis and is still under development.
- **Aggregate Function:** This second process is responsible for performing some data aggregations based on the tags extracted in the previous process. The output aggregates contain a summary (number of positive/negative/neutral tweets and an average score) split with a concrete periodicity (second/minute/hour/and more) for a given period of time. The need to include the ontology/taxonomy used in the named-entity recognition process as part of this aggregation process is still being discussed. This ontology might be used for enriching the aggregation with the different categories represented in the ontology.

Following the design implemented for the document-based sentiment delivered for release 1, this aggregated function is provided as Apache NiFi workflows and executed with parametrized python code to be connected to the Apache NiFi instance and initialized with concrete variables.

D4.2 [36] provides additional details on how this approach was implemented in the sentiment analysis released for the 1st prototype.

2.1.4.3 SUMMARY OF CHANGES: OPINION MINING & SENTIMENT ANALYSIS

This second release is focused on upgrading the sentiment analysis provided in the PolicyCLOUD project by:

- providing a new entity-level sentiment analysis based on deep learning approaches such as the use of BERT models.
- enhancing the entity-level sentiment through BERT-based NER and entities/aspect extraction based on ontologies.

2.1.5 Social Dynamics & Behavioural Data Analytics

We describe the second prototype for the Social Dynamics component of the PolicyCLOUD project. We refer to this component as Politika. Currently Politika runs as a stand-alone web application on the cloud.

2.1.5.1 SUMMARY OF CHANGES: SOCIAL DYNAMICS AND BEHAVIOURAL DATA ANALYTICS

Compared to the first version as described in deliverable D4.2 Politika has been extended to accept as input and simulate policies consisting of multiple goals, alternatives and simulation models. All these operations have been supported by extending the Politika GUI with new capabilities for the interactive editing and simulation of policies and of the social network on which they are applied. Furthermore, the Politika GUI has been enriched with 2D and 3D animations of the state of the social network after each simulation cycle.

2.1.5.2 THE STRUCTURE OF SIMULATION MODELS FOR POLICY ALTERNATIVES

Politika takes as input a graph corresponding to a social network and simulates its dynamics using the agent-based modelling paradigm. Politika allows the user to:

- specify, edit or delete a simulation
- browse the specifications of simulations stored in the system
- execute simulations
- upload/download data to/from a simulation
- examine raw simulation results
- compute and visualize simulation analytics

Politika's output is the social network that results after the simulation of the dynamics of its input, and it is represented as a graph.

The Social Dynamics component uses a special-purpose language for specifying modelling individual, connection and policy attributes and dynamics. In particular, the user specifies modelling attributes as keyword/value strings. For example:

```
incubation_period: 5, infection_period: 10, immunity_period: 10,  
cur_icu_units: 0
```

represent the policy parameters for a containment policy in an epidemiological context. Strings ending in `:` are keyword names for parameters, while the rest are the parameter values.

Individual, connection and policy dynamics as specified as IF . . DO rules. For example:

```
IF  this.cur_icu_units > 0 and
this.cur_infection_death_prob >
this.baseline_infection_death_prob
DO
this.cur_infection_death_prob:
max(this.cur_infection_death_prob
0.1*this.cur_infection_death_prob,
this.baseline_infection_death_prob)
```

represents a policy dynamic rule that decreases the current infection death probability if it is above the baseline probability provided there are icu units available.

In particular, the IF part describes a sequence of logical conditions (and, or, not) that need to be satisfied for the rule to fire, while the DO part describes new assignments for the attributes of the entity (individual, connection or policy) executing the rule. Multiple statements in the DO part are separated with the `;` marker, while different rules are separated with the `~` marker. In the case of individual attributes, the keyword `this` refers to the current individual executing the rule. The current value of such an attribute is accessed using the period (.) followed by the attribute name. For example, `this.name` refers to the name attribute of the individual executing this rule. The assignment operator is `:=`, therefore the statement:

```
this.name := "Nick"
```

assigns a new value for the attribute `name` of the current individual.

In the case of connections, the keyword `edge` refers to the connection executing the current rule, the keyword `this` refers to the individual from which the connection originates while the keyword `distal` refers to the individual that is the target of the connection.

This special-purpose language has a set of built-in functions that can help the modeler in developing her social simulation. The specifications for these functions along with the rest of the Politika API are described in the reference manual for Politika at: <http://epinoetic.org/Politika/doc/api-reference.html>

2.1.5.3 THE STRUCTURE OF POLICY MODELS

Each policy model is represented as a tree structure in JSON format. For example, figure 12 provides a screenshot of a policy model for radicalization control stored in the system. As the figure indicates each Policy contains a list of Goals. Each Goal contains a list of Alternatives. Each Alternative contains a list of Steps that refer to simulation models stored in the system.

Radicalization Control

[\[Clone\]](#) [\[Edit\]](#) [\[Delete\]](#)

- **Description:** Explores alternatives for curtailing radicals influence in a social group
- **Goals:** `{0 => {criteria: {adequacy: "radicals.avg < sympathizers.avg and sympathizers.avg < conformists.avg"}, description: "Restrict Radicals Influence", goal: 0, objectives: {0 => {description: "Maintain Status Quo", goal: 0, objective: 0, policy: 1, repetitions: 4, results: {1 => "{conformism_threshold: 0, conformists: 0.42, friendship_threshold: 0, radicalization_threshold: 0.5, radicals: 0.56, sympathizers: 0.02}", 2 => "{conformism_threshold: 0, conformists: 0.44, friendship_threshold: 0, radicalization_threshold: 0.5, radicals: 0.56, sympathizers: 0.0}", 3 => "{conformism_threshold: 0, conformists: 0.46, friendship_threshold: 0, radicalization_threshold: 0.5, radicals: 0.54, sympathizers: 0.0}", 4 => "{conformism_threshold: 0, conformists: 0.44, friendship_threshold: 0, radicalization_threshold: 0.5, radicals: 0.54, sympathizers: 0.02}"}, statistics: {conformism_threshold: {avg: 0.0, max: 0, min: 0}, conformists: {avg: 0.44, max: 0.46, min: 0.42}, friendship_threshold: {avg: 0.0, max: 0, min: 0}, radicalization_threshold: {avg: 0.5, max: 0.5, min: 0.5}, radicals: {avg: 0.55, max: 0.56, min: 0.54}, sympathizers: {avg: 0.01, max: 0.02, min: 0.0}}, steps: {0 => {description: "Base case with No Policy", goal: 0, objective: 0, policy: "1", results: "[]", simulation: {id: 1, new_dataset?: true}, step: 0, type: "step"}}, type: "objective"}, 1 => {description: "Restrict radicals", goal: 0, objective: 1, policy: 1, repetitions: 4, results: {1 => "{conformism_threshold: 0, conformists: 0.54, friendship_threshold: 0, radicalization_threshold: 0.5, radicals: 0.44, restricted: 0.08, restriction_threshold: 0.5, sympathizers: 0.02}", 2 => "{conformism_threshold: 0, conformists: 0.64, friendship_threshold: 0, radicalization_threshold: 0.5, radicals: 0.36, restricted: 0.08, restriction_threshold: 0.5, sympathizers: 0.0}", 3 => "{conformism_threshold: 0, conformists: 0.54, friendship_threshold: 0, radicalization_threshold: 0.5, radicals: 0.4, restricted: 0.26, restriction_threshold: 0.5, sympathizers: 0.06}", 4 => "{conformism_threshold: 0, conformists: 0.58, friendship_threshold: 0, radicalization_threshold: 0.5, radicals: 0.42, restricted: 0.22, restriction_threshold: 0.5, sympathizers: 0.0}"}, statistics: {conformism_threshold: {avg: 0.0, max: 0, min: 0}, conformists: {avg: 0.5750000000000001, max: 0.64, min: 0.54}, friendship_threshold: {avg: 0.0, max: 0, min: 0}, radicalization_threshold: {avg: 0.5, max: 0.5, min: 0.5}, radicals: {avg: 0.405, max: 0.44, min: 0.36}, restricted: {avg: 0.16, max: 0.26, min: 0.08}, restriction_threshold: {avg: 0.5, max: 0.5, min: 0.5}, sympathizers: {avg: 0.02, max: 0.06, min: 0.0}}, steps: {0 => {description: "Apply restriction policy to radicals", goal: 0, objective: 1, policy: "1", results: "[]", simulation: {id: 3, new_dataset?: true}, step: 0, type: "step"}}, type: "objective"}}, policy: 1, population_gen: "max_edges: 2, min_edges: 1, directed?: false, degree_distribution: :homogeneous", results: {adequacy: {0 => false, 1 => false}}, type: "goal"}}`
- **Distribution:** Public
- **Contact:** a@a.com

FIGURE 12 - SCREENSHOT OF A STORED POLICY MODEL IN POLITIKA

2.1.6 Operational Data Repository

An integral part of the central data repository of PolicyCLOUD is the operational datastore provided by LXS. It is a relational database that provides support both for SQL and NoSQL executions, ensuring transactional semantics and ACID properties under very high rated data ingestion workload, due to its scalable transactional processing mechanism and the provision of an additional interface that can store data directly to its storage, bypassing the introduced footprint added by the relational query engine of the data store. As a result, it can provide support both for static data ingestion via a batch process and for ingestion of streaming data. Its functionality and features have been documented in the D4.3 [34] deliverable under section 5.3. In the scope of WP4, it has been integrated on one hand with the mechanisms developed in the scope of the DAA API Gateway, as the final component in the data ingestion pipeline deployed by the latter will be the persistent storage of the data items into the operational datastore. Additionally, it has been integrated with those of the components developed under the scope of WP4, as analytical tools, that have the need to consume data from the persistent medium which is, at first phase, the operational datastore.

2.2 Interfaces

This section provides the description and details of the component interfaces.

2.2.1 DAA API Gateway

Following are the DAA API Gateway API. The API can be invoked with a command line or Rest interface.

2.2.1.1 SUMMARY OF CHANGES: DAA API GATEWAY

Notable changes include: use cases api examples, Image based Analytic function registration (to support large analytic function implementations), addition of legal aspects in datasource and analytic functions registration and centralized logging mechanism. Initial DAA API included future fields which were not used in SW1 usecases integration and are now integrated in SW2.

2.2.1.2 ANALYTIC FUNCTION REGISTRATION

Register the analytic function as an action in OpenWhisk.

Parameters:

1. name: function name
2. kind: blackbox for image based functions, java:8/python:3 for java 8/ python 3 small footprint functions
3. filename: jar filename containing the function code
4. main: specify the function main class
5. image: this parameter has to be specified if the “kind” is “blackbox”. In this case it should include the image name residing in the container registry service function parameters: function parameters (Json)
6. type: analytic / analytic-ingest

7. category: Data-Cleaning / Data-Interoperability / Situational-Knowledge / Opinion-Mining / Social-Dynamic
8. description: function description and usage
9. Expected input data schema/format
10. graph: graph format supported by PDT
11. policy: policy domain supported by PDT
12. purpose: for data access enforcement
13. biasDoc – this parameter permits, and in fact could even oblige (e.g., by checking that this parameter has a minimal required length and/or that an attachment of a defined format and filesize range is included), the Analytic Owners to input bias management documentation, providing information on the specific measures taken to address the risk of biases inherent to the functioning of the Analytics Ingest Function. It could also permit / oblige Analytic Owners to upload or indicate one or more unit test datasets on which the Analytics Ingest Function can be applied, so as to demonstrate that resulting bias measurements do not exceed a given maximum (in other words, that the specific measures taken to address the risk of biases are functioning effectively, as intended);
14. tradeoffsDoc - this parameter permits, and in fact could even oblige (e.g., by checking that this parameter has a minimal required length and/or that an attachment of a defined format and filesize range is included), the Analytic Owners to input documentation on the management of trade-offs, providing information on the relevant trade-offs encountered, decisions made concerning the balancing of competing requirements (e.g., result precision versus fairness) and measures taken to implement and document those decisions.

Return: success / failure

Spec: Register the function with all associated metadata (provided in the parameters) in OpenWhisk.

Each ingest function is expected to read the incoming data from the request's message parameter (JSON string), and to return the transformed message as a json string.

The result JSON string might be the input of the next ingest function, or the transformation result written to PolicyCloud's backend.

Return indicates whether analytic function successfully created as an action in OpenWhisk

Implementation details:

Analytic functions are developed by Analytic owners and can be implemented either in python or in java or node.js. and should follow OpenWhisk action implementation guidelines.

DAA uses a common GitLab structure for functions' code registry and a common container registry for functions' docker images with all required dependencies.

Files and images are automatically pulled from the PolicyCLOUD GitLab service during function registration to create the serverless function.

Function name should be unique.

Filename parameter specifies the filename containing the function code written under OpenWhisk conventions¹ placed in the packaged-functions directory under the PolicyCLOUD project GitLab repository.

Main parameter specifies the main function in the above function code specified by the filename parameter.

In SW2 several types are supported: java:8, python:4 and blackbox.

java:8 type:

Use cases implementing functions in DAA should follow the guidelines to generate the jar:

- java version 8 is supported
- All dependencies should be packaged in the jar, and the jar total size should be under 48MB
- jar file should be uploaded to the PolicyCLOUD GitHub repository packaged-functions folder:
- maven has to be installed
- If the analytic function has external dependencies, they should be specified in pom.xml
- Sample functions jar called ReferenceFunctions.jar can be found in the project GitLab as a reference implementation for jar containing external dependencies
- Run maven clean and package to create the jar file (mvn package -Dmaven.test.skip=true)

python:3 type:

- python3 is supported
- All dependencies should be packaged in the zip, and the zip total size should be under 48MB
- zip file should be uploaded to the PolicyCLOUD github repository packaged-functions folder
- see <https://github.com/apache/openwhisk/blob/master/docs/actions-python.md>
- There should be a file named `__main__.py`, returning json
- Python code should be packaged into Openwhisk action
- Sample implementation file can be found in the project GitLab as a reference implementation/daa/src/main/python/ibm.functions/sample1

blackbox type:

For functions exceeding size > 48MB use blackbox type and provide a docker file with all dependencies as well as packaged analytic code.

Docker images should be uploaded to the project's container registry, and packaged code to the dedicated GitLab repo folder.

Python analytic example:

All dependencies should be specified in requirements.txt

Create Dockerfile

FROM openwhisk/actionloop-python-v3.7

COPY requirements.txt requirements.txt

RUN pip install --upgrade pip setuptools six && pip install --no-cache-dir -r requirements.txt

¹ <https://github.com/apache/openwhisk/blob/master/docs/actions-java.md>

```
docker build -t <IMAGE_NAME> .
```

Package analytic code: zip all files + __main.py__

Purpose and access policies are out of scope for SW2

Rest interface: PUT /analytic-function

The following command is an example for the registration of a cleaning **ingest** function:

```
curl -k -X PUT https://90.147.75.136:31001/api/v1/web/policycloud/daa/analytic-function -H
'Content-Type: application/json' -d '{"name": "clean", "kind": "blackbox", "image":
"registry.grid.ece.ntua.gr:5050/oshrit/daa/cleanfunction:latest", "filename": "action.zip", "main":
"loadData", "function_parameters": "{}", "type": "analytic-ingest", "category": "cleaning",
"description": "cleaning and interoperability", "biasDoc": "", "tradeoffsDoc": ""}'
```

an example of an **analytic function** registration for a SentimentAggregator:

```
curl -k -X PUT https://90.147.75.136:31001/api/v1/web/policycloud/daa/analytic-function -H
'Content-Type: application/json' -d '{
  "name":"SentimentAggregator",
  "kind":"blackbox",
  "filename": "sentimentAggregatorLXCFunction_docker.zip",
  "image":"registry.grid.ece.ntua.gr:5050/oshrit/daa/sentiment_nifi_ow",
  "function_parameters":{"{
    \"unit\":null,
    \"valueType\": \"DATETIME\",
    \"name\": \"start_date\",
    \"description\": \"the date to start retrieving sentiments\",
    \"inputType\": \"VARIABLE\",
    \"id\": \"a86fe026-b17c-497a-8716-f4d1960616fc\",
    \"evaluationTypesAllowed\": [\"EQUAL\"],
    \"valueConstraints\": [],
    \"required\": true}, {
      \"unit\":null, \"valueType\": \"DATETIME\", \"name\": \"end_date\",
      \"description\": \"the date to end retrieving sentiments\",
      \"inputType\": \"VARIABLE\",
      \"id\": \"03d31711-2614-491d-90b4-ac055fdaad3a\",
      \"evaluationTypesAllowed\": [\"EQUAL\"], \"valueConstraints\": [],
      \"required\": true}, { \"unit\":null, \"valueType\": \"STRING\",
      \"name\": \"per\", \"description\": \"the periodicity\",
      \"inputType\": \"VARIABLE\",
      \"id\": \"13d8b18f-0671-4081-ac1b-842777540b66\",
      \"evaluationTypesAllowed\": [\"EQUAL\"], \"required\": true,
```

```

    "valueConstraints": [ { "constraintType": "VALUESALLOWED",
                          "value": [ "second", "minute", "hour", "day" ] } ],
    "graph": [ "TIME_SERIES", "GAUGE" ],
    "policydomain": [ "AGRIFOOD" ],
    "type": "analytic-analysis",
    "category": "Opinion Mining & Sentiment Analysis",
    "description": "Aggregation of tweets based on the sentiment analysis performed for a
given period of time",
    "biasDoc": "This string expresses the bias documentation",
    "tradeoffsDoc": "This string expresses the tradeoffs documentation"
}'

```

The following example is for the registration of an heatmap analytic function:

```

curl -k -X PUT 90.147.75.136:31001/api/v1/web/policycloud/daa/analytic-function -H 'Content-
Type: application/json' -d '{
  "name": "HeatMap",
  "kind": "java:8",
  "filename": "heatMap-0.0.1-SNAPSHOT.jar",
  "main": "atos.ari.data.policyCloud.heatMap.HeatMap ",
  "function_parameters": "[ { \"name\": \"year\", \"unit\": \"unit\", \"description\":
\"param_description\", \"valueType\": \"STRING\", \"valueConstraints\": [ { \"constraintType\":
\"DEFAULT\", \"evaluationTypesAllowed\":
[ \"EQUAL\", \"GREATER\", \"GREATER_OR_EQUAL\", \"LESS\", \"LESS_OR_EQUAL\", \"value\":
\"default value\" ] }, { \"inputType\": \"VARIABLE\", \"required\": \"True\", \"value\": { \"type\":
\"EQUAL\", \"value\": \"2004\" } }, { \"name\": \"region\", \"unit\": \"unit\", \"description\":
\"param_description\", \"valueType\": \"STRING\", \"valueConstraints\": [ { \"constraintType\":
\"DEFAULT\", \"value\": \"default value\" }, \"evaluationTypesAllowed\":
[ \"EQUAL\", \"GREATER\", \"GREATER_OR_EQUAL\", \"LESS\", \"LESS_OR_EQUAL\", \"inputType\":
\"VARIABLE\", \"required\": true, \"value\": { \"type\": \"IN\", \"values\": [ \"8\", \"1\" ] } } ] ",
  "graph": [ "HEATMAP_POI" ],
  "policydomain": [ "SECURITY" ],
  "type": "analytic-analysis",
  "category": "Situational-Knowledge",
  "description": "exploratory analysis in the form of data aggregations exhibiting the
incidence of certain events",
  "biasDoc": "This string expresses the bias documentation",
  "tradeoffsDoc": "This string expresses the tradeoffs documentation"
}'

```

2.2.1.3 DATA SOURCE REGISTRATION

Import a data source into the database by applying ingest functions on it.

Parameters:

1. Name
2. Type (Streaming / Ingest-now / External)
3. Description
4. Source specification (streaming details, source data location, source URL, access method, credentials etc.)
5. Schema / metadata
6. Permissions – by whom (public / specified user list) and for what purpose the data can be used for (Analytics Functions which are to be applied to a Data Source should have been registered for purposes which are identical or compatible with the purposes identified for that Data Source)
7. Analytics Ingest Function + parameters if applicable
8. biasDoc – this parameter permits, and in fact could even oblige (e.g., by checking that this parameter has a minimal required length and/or that an attachment of a defined format and filesize range is included), the Data Owner to input bias management documentation, providing information on the bias detection methods applied to the Data Source, the specific biases identified, and the specific measures taken to address any such biases.
9. GDPRDoc – this parameter permits, and in fact could even oblige (e.g., by checking that this parameter has a minimal required length and/or that an attachment of a defined format and filesize range is included), the Data Owners to input privacy / data protection management documentation which, in particular, should indicate whether any personal data is included within the Data Source and, if so, the measures taken to ensure that the Data Source can be ingested onto the platform in compliance with the applicable data protection and regulatory framework related to the processing of personal data, as defined by the GDPR and other applicable data protection laws (e.g., to ensure compliance with the principles of lawfulness, transparency and purpose limitation under the GDPR, considering the purposes for which the personal data within the Data Source were originally collected and the purposes for which those personal data will be further processed via the platform).
10. authDoc – this parameter, permits, and in fact could even oblige (e.g., by checking that this parameter has a minimal required length and/or that an attachment of a defined format and filesize range is included), the Data Owners to input documentation to demonstrate that the registration of the Data Source has been authorised by relevant rightsholders (or that such authorisation is not required under applicable laws).

Return: success / fail

Spec:

1. Data source name should be unique.
2. Create the functions chain (in this prototype we demonstrate only a single function) involving Kafka topics and OpenWhisk triggers and rules, from the Kafka input topic (written into by the Cloud Gateway) to the resulting table in the DB. Create DB table.
In SW2: Creates input (T1) and output (R1) topics in Kafka, creates an action sequence with the ingest function and Kafka producer

3. Invokes Cloud Gateway task which retrieves the data source content and place it in T1 topic
4. Register the data source with its metadata

Implementation details:

1. Supported types in SW2: Ingest-now and streaming
2. T1 and R1 topic names are derived from the data source name.
3. The Cloud Gateway task is supplied with the url, Access parameters, Schema, T1 topic, and Type. It is responsible on reading the data accordingly and placing it in T1 topic
 - On Ingest-now – a simple chunks loop to place the content as messages in T1 topic
 - On Streaming – a periodic thread to place incoming streams as messages in T1 topicOpenWhisk triggers and rules created subscribe to T1 topic. Once a message was placed in the topic, the ingest-function given is invoked and the resulting new dataset is placed in R1, which in turn is written to the database.
4. The name of the data source in the DAA and the name of the data source backed table is the data source given name (Name parameter).
5. Cloud Gateway component is called to pull the dataset from the given URL

Rest interface: PUT /datasource

The following example is for the registration of a streaming datasource, with sentiment ingest function:

```
curl -k -X PUT https://90.147.75.136:31001/api/v1/web/policycloud/daa/datasource -H 'Content-Type: application/json' -d '{
  "ingest_functions": ["sentiment", "leanxcale-sentiment"],
  "name": "tweet-carinena",
  "keyword": "carinena",
  "type": "stream",
  "description": "Carinena tweets",
  "access": { "type": "kafka" },
  "schema": {"name": "statuses"},
  "permissions": "UNKNOWN_PERMISSIONS",
  "url": https://api.twitter.com/1.1/search/tweets,
  "biasDoc": "This string expresses the bias documentation",
  "gdprDoc": "This string expresses the GDPR documentation",
  "authDoc": "This string expresses the authorizations documentation"
}'
```

2.2.1.4 LIST REGISTERED FUNCTIONS

Display a detailed list of registered functions

Parameters:

1. Type: analytic / analytic-ingest

Return: List of all registered functions (analytic or analytic-ingest), each with its metadata

Rest interface: GET /analytic-function?type=

Get detailed list of all the resisted functions

```
curl -X GET "https://$URL/api/v1/web/policycloud/daa/analytic-function.http?type=analytic-analysis"
```

result example:

```
[
  {
    "name": "HeatMap",
    "parameters": [
      {
        "key": "description",
        "value": "exploratory analysis in the form of data aggregations exhibiting the incidence of certain events"
      },
      "key": "function_parameters",
      "value": [
        {
          "description": "param_description",
          "inputType": "VARIABLE",
          "name": "iyear",
          "required": "True",
          "unit": "unit",
          "value": {
            "type": "EQUAL",
            "value": "2004"
          }
        },
        "valueConstraints": [
          {
            "constraintType": "DEFAULT",
            "evaluationTypesAllowed": [
              "EQUAL",
              "GREATER",
              "GREATER_OR_EQUAL",
              "LESS",
              "LESS_OR_EQUAL"
            ],
            "value": "default value"
          }
        ],
        "valueType": "STRING"
      }
    ],
    ...},
  {
    "name": "SentimentAggregator",
```

```
"parameters": [
  {
    "key": "description",
    "value": "Aggregation of tweets based on the sentiment analysis performed for a given period of time"
  },
  {
    "key": "function_parameters",
    "value": [
      {
        "description": "the date to start retrieving sentiments",
        "evaluationTypesAllowed": [
          "EQUAL"
        ],
        "id": "a86fe026-b17c-497a-8716-f4d1960616fc",
        "inputType": "VARIABLE",
        "name": "start_date",
        "required": true,
        "unit": null,
        "valueConstraints": [],
        "valueType": "DATETIME"
      }
    ]
  },
  ...
}]
```

2.2.1.5 LIST REGISTERED DATA SOURCES

Parameters: None

Return: List of all registered data sources, each with its metadata (including the actual DBTable)

Rest interface: GET /datasource

Get detailed list of all the resisted functions

curl -k -X GET [https://\\$URL:31001/api/v1/web/policycloud/daa/datasource](https://$URL:31001/api/v1/web/policycloud/daa/datasource)

result example:

```
[
  {
    "name": "gtd",
    "parameters": [
      {
        "key": "description",
        "value": "Terrorist incidents"
      },
      {
        "key": "type",
        "value": "ingest"
      }
    ],
    ...
  }
  {
    "name": "sentiments",
    "parameters": [
      {
```

```
"key": "description",
"value": "Carinena tweets"
},
{
  "key": "type",
  "value": "stream"
},
....
}]
```

2.2.1.6 APPLY FUNCTION

Invoke the requested analytics on the requested data source

Parameters:

1. UserCredentials: (TBD where is the enforcement point)
2. Function: Analytic function name
3. Parameters: for the function (Json)
4. Data-source: data source name

Return: jobId/json result

Spec:

1. Invoke the OpenWhisk function (with the Parameters and data source (db table))
2. Return the OpenWhisk jobId if asynchronous. The function result in json for synchronous

Implementation details:

Job id is a wrapper for OpenWhisk activation id

Rest interface: POST / analytic-function

The following is for an Heatmap invocation on gtd datasource:

```
curl -k -X POST https://90.147.75.136:31001/api/v1/web/policycloud/daa/analytic-function -H 'Content-Type: application/json' -d '{
```

```
"function": "HeatMap",
```

```
"datasource": "gtd",
```

```
"parameters":
```

```
{
  "datasource": "GTD",
  "arguments": {
    "parameters": [
      {"unit": "iyear",
       "valueType": "STRING",
       "name": "iyear",
       "description": "theYearsRange",
```



```
"inputType":"VARIABLE",
"id":"ee80842a-6fa2-42ef-bd97-6d98629555ff",
"evaluationTypesAllowed":["RANGE"],
"valueConstraints":[],
"value":{
  "valueMax":2004,
  "valueMin":2004,
  "type":"RANGE"
},
"required":true,
{
  "unit":"region",
  "valueType":"STRING",
  "name":"region",
  "description":"alistofregions",
  "inputType":"VARIABLE",
  "id":"31303d88-281c-49bf-9703-2097d9745df2",
  "evaluationTypesAllowed":["IN"],
  "valueConstraints":[],
  "value":{
    "values":["1","8"],
    "type":"IN"
  },
  "required":true,
{
  "unit":null,
  "valueType":"FLOAT",
  "name":"jobid",
  "description":"theidofthenewlycreatedjob",
  "inputType":"SYSTEM",
  "id":"a17e21ac-dad2-4fba-bb39-8f72b4c0a41c",
  "evaluationTypesAllowed":["EQUAL"],
  "valueConstraints":[],
  "value":{
    "type":"EQUAL",
    "value":1
  },
  "required":null,
{
  "unit":null,
  "valueType":"STRING",
  "name":"graph",
  "description":"thetargetoutputvisualizationgraph",
  "inputType":"SYSTEM",
  "id":"5bbb0b0a-b740-44cf-beae-e4ac2ff52a54",
  "evaluationTypesAllowed":["EQUAL"],
  "valueConstraints":[],
  "value":{
    "type":"EQUAL",
    "value":"HEATMAP_POI"
  },
  "required":null}
}
}
}
```

Example of Sentiment aggregator invocation of sentiments datasource:


```
curl -k -X POST https://90.147.75.136:31001/api/v1/web/policycloud/daa/analytic-  
function -H 'Content-Type: application/json' -d '{  
  "datasource":"tweet-carinena",  
  "function":"SentimentAggregator",  
  "parameters":  
  
  {  
    "datasource":"tweet-carinena",  
    "arguments": {  
      "dataBase": {  
        "urlIDB":"jdbc:leanxcale://90.147.170.166:1529/SARGA; user=APP",  
        "user":"APP",  
        "table":"SENTIMENTS"  
      },  
      "parameters":  
      [  
        { "unit":null,  
          "valueType":"DATETIME",  
          "name":"start_date",  
          "description":"the date to start retrieving sentiments",  
          "inputType":"VARIABLE",  
          "id":"a86fe026-b17c-497a-8716-f4d1960616fc",  
          "evaluationTypesAllowed":["EQUAL"],  
          "valueConstraints":[],  
          "value": {  
            "type":"EQUAL",  
            "value":"2021-03-10 11:10:21"  
          },  
          "required":true  
        },  
        { "unit":null,  
          "valueType":"DATETIME",  
          "name":"end_date",  
          "description":"the date to end retrieving sentiments",  
          "inputType":"VARIABLE",  
          "id":"03d31711-2614-491d-90b4-ac055fdaad3a",  
          "evaluationTypesAllowed":["EQUAL"],  
          "valueConstraints":[],  
          "value":{  
            "type":"EQUAL",  
            "value":"2021-03-11 00:10:21"  
          },  
          "required":true  
        },  
        { "unit":null,  
          "valueType":"STRING",  
          "name":"per",  
          "description":"the periodicity",  
          "inputType":"VARIABLE",  
          "id":"13d8b18f-0671-4081-ac1b-842777540b66",  
          "evaluationTypesAllowed":["EQUAL"],  
          "valueConstraints": [  
            { "constraintType":"VALUESALLOWED",  
              "value":["second","minute","hour","day"]  
            }  
          ],  
          "value":{  
            "type":"EQUAL",
```



```
        "value":"hour"
    },
    "required":true
  },
  {"unit":null,
  "valueType":"FLOAT",
  "name":"jobid",
  "description":"the id of the newly created job",
  "inputType":"SYSTEM",
  "id":"8ef9f6af-ee06-42d8-8a62-2dc00655a7f5",
  "evaluationTypesAllowed":["EQUAL"],
  "valueConstraints":[],
  "value":{
    "type":"EQUAL",
    "value":5
  },
  "required":true
},
{"unit":null,
"valueType":"STRING",
"name":"graph",
"description":"the target output visualization graph",
"inputType":"SYSTEM",
"id":"ad852988-7b9f-4dc2-b676-9d2e4d5a5646",
"evaluationTypesAllowed":["EQUAL"],
"valueConstraints":[],
"value":{
  "type":"EQUAL",
  "value":"GAUGE"
},
"required":true
},
{"unit":null,
"valueType":"STRING",
"name":"pdt_results",
"description":"the url of the service to send the results",
"inputType":"SYSTEM",
"id":"0030259d-259a-4963-b132-46e03621dfc7",
"evaluationTypesAllowed":["EQUAL"],
"valueConstraints":[],
"value":{
  "type":"EQUAL",
  "value":"http://90.147.102.215:54735/pdt/jobs"
},
"required":true}
]]}'
```

2.2.1.7 GET JOB STATUS

Return the job result

Parameters:

1. jobID: id of the job

Return: Working / Completed / Failed, function json result

Spec:

1. Used for invoking asynchronous functions on data source
2. Return the job status, if completed return the function json result in the body

Implementation details:

In SW2 when the job is completed – returns the result of the invocation of the function on the data source (json) in the body. error - if job id is not found or job is not completed.

Job id is a wrapper for OpenWhisk activation id

Rest interface: GET /analytic-function?job_id=

curl -k -X GET [https://\\$URL:31001/api/v1/web/policycloud/daa/analytic-function?job_id=123](https://$URL:31001/api/v1/web/policycloud/daa/analytic-function?job_id=123)

2.2.2 Centralized Logging

2.2.2.1 SUMMARY OF CHANGES: CENTRALIZED LOGGING

New service. This service did not exist in D4.2.

2.2.2.2 DETAILS OF THE LOGGING SERVICE

Appends an additional entry in the centralized log file(s).

Parameters:

1. project: project name, e.g. PolicyCloud
2. wp: work package name, e.g. daa
3. action: action name log is sent from
4. type: action type log is sent from
5. name: name of the analytic function/dataset
6. user: username if applicable
7. message: log message
8. level: log severity level

Return: Log appended

Implementation details:

The logging service is accessible to all PolicyCLOUD WPs using an HTTP API, and forms a centralized, project-wide infrastructure component. Each logging event is stored in a persistent filesystem enabled by NFS and ensures resiliency to pod failures and restarts.

This service appends an additional entry in the centralized log file(s). The list of fields logged may be modified to fit the message which is created. It is recommended to include the following fields: project, wp, action, type, name, user, message and level for all log messages to form standard structure.

Rest interface: PUT /policycloud/daa

Example of PolicyCLOUD logging event:

```
curl -H "content-type: application/json" -XPUT 'http://90.147.75.129:8088/policycloud/daa' -d '{
  "project": "policycloud",
  "wp" : "daa",
  "action": "register",
  "type": "stream",
  "name": "ds1",
  "user" : "myUserName",
  "message" : "Registering new datasource",
  "level": "info"
}'
```

2.2.3 Enhanced Interoperability & Data Cleaning

2.2.3.1 SUMMARY OF CHANGES: Enhanced Interoperability & Data Cleaning

For this second release, both the Enhanced Interoperability and Data Cleaning components are provided and can be utilized as dedicated functions through corresponding endpoints. In addition, the file, in JSON format, on which these functions will be implemented is also needed as parameter in contrary to what was documented in the D4.2.

2.2.3.2 DATA CLEANING COMPONENT

The incoming HTTP requests are handled by the DataCleanerController, while the execution of the workflow is performed by the DataCleaningService. Through the provided interface the following endpoint is offered: Data Cleaning endpoint. This endpoint is responsible for handling the data cleaning workflow execution requests and providing the updated data (cleaned data) as a result of the execution. To access the Data Cleaning endpoint, the latter expects the data (either historical or streaming) for which the data cleaning workflow will be executed. The Data Cleaning endpoint is documented below:

Spec:

Initiates the data cleaning workflow and provides the estimated results.

Endpoint URL:

http://hostname[:port]/cleaning/{file}

HTTP method:

POST

Parameters:

file: A JSON file that contains the input data to be cleaned.

2.2.3.3 ENHANCED INTEROPERABILITY COMPONENT

The incoming HTTP requests are handled by the InteroperabilityController while the execution of the workflow is performed by the InteroperabilityService. Through the provided interface the following endpoint is offered: Interoperability endpoint. This endpoint is responsible for handling the enhanced interoperability workflow as provided through the utilization of the SemAI mechanism. To access the Enhanced Interoperability endpoint, the latter expects the dataset for which the SemAI mechanism will be executed in JSON format. The final exposed Enhanced Interoperability endpoint is documented below:

Spec:

Initiates the enhanced interoperability workflow and provides the estimated results.

Endpoint URL:

http://hostname[:port]/interoperability/{file}

HTTP method:

POST

Parameters:

file: A JSON file that contains the input data to be cleaned.

2.2.4 Situational Knowledge Acquisition & Analysis

2.2.4.1 SUMMARY OF CHANGES: Situational Knowledge Acquisition & Analysis

The changes between the first and second prototypes can be found in "Summary of change: Situational Knowledge Acquisition & Analysis" in 2.1.3.2.

2.2.4.2 SKA EDA 1ST PROTOTYPE INPUT PARAMETERS

For the case of the SKA-EDA v1, any variable belonging to a database can be included as variables in the frequency distribution (across one or multiple categories), in the accumulation distribution and in the geographical distribution. The command-line interface is as shown in the picture below:

```
usage: SKA_EDA_v0.1.py [-h] --useCase USECASE --datasetFolder DATASETFOLDER
                    [--frequencyDistribution FREQUENCYDISTRIBUTION]
                    [--accumulatedDistribution ACCUMULATEDDISTRIBUTION]
                    [--geographicalDistribution GEOGRAPHICALDISTRIBUTION]
                    [--initQueryDate INITQUERYDATE] [--endQueryDate ENDQUERYDATE]
                    [--variable1 VARIABLE1] [--variable2 VARIABLE2] [--stacked STACKED]
                    [--head HEAD] [--yAxesName YAXESNAME] [--datasetName DATASETNAME] [--name NAME]
                    [--description DESCRIPTION]

optional arguments:
  -h, --help            show this help message and exit
  --useCase USECASE, -rd USECASE
                        REQUIRED. set the use case: uc3, uc4. If not particular distribution are set,
                        it computes a pre-defined package of distributions for each use case
  --datasetFolder DATASETFOLDER, -p DATASETFOLDER
                        REQUIRED. set the path to the folder containing the dataset in csv o xlsx format
  --frequencyDistribution FREQUENCYDISTRIBUTION, -fd FREQUENCYDISTRIBUTION
                        Distribution of observations across multiples categories. It can be done across
                        one variable or two
  --accumulatedDistribution ACCUMULATEDDISTRIBUTION, -ad ACCUMULATEDDISTRIBUTION
                        Accumulation of one variable across multiple categories. It needs at least two
                        variables
  --geographicalDistribution GEOGRAPHICALDISTRIBUTION, -gd GEOGRAPHICALDISTRIBUTION
                        Group large amounts of data accross a geolocalional variable
  --initQueryDate INITQUERYDATE, -iD INITQUERYDATE
                        init Date for limiting the results
  --endQueryDate ENDQUERYDATE, -eD ENDQUERYDATE
                        end Date for limitin the results
  --variable1 VARIABLE1, -v1 VARIABLE1
                        variable 1 for the frequency distribution calculation
  --variable2 VARIABLE2, -v2 VARIABLE2
                        variable 2 for the frequency distributioun and accumulated distribution
                        calculation
  --stacked STACKED, -s STACKED
                        if the biVariable distribution is staket or not
  --head HEAD, -he HEAD
                        Reduce by the N most repeated values (mode) in variable 2
  --yAxesName YAXESNAME, -yName YAXESNAME
                        Name of the yAxesName
  --datasetName DATASETNAME, -dn DATASETNAME
                        Name of the used dataset
  --name NAME, -n NAME
                        Name of the visualization
  --description DESCRIPTION, -des DESCRIPTION
                        Description of the visualization
```

FIGURE 13 - SKA-EDA_V1 INPUT PARAMETERS

Where:

- useCase: Set the use case: UC3, UC4. If no particular distribution is set, it computes a pre-defined package of distributions for each use case, required=True
- datasetFolder: Set the path to the folder containing the dataset in csv or xlsx format, required=True
- frequencyDistribution: Distribution of observations across multiple categories. It can be done across one variable or two
- accumulatedDistribution: Accumulation of one variable across multiple categories. It needs at least two variables
- geographicalDistribution (gd): Group large amounts of data across a geolocal variable
- initQueryDate: init Date for limiting the results
- endQueryDate: end Date for limiting the results
- variable1 (v1): variable 1 for the distribution calculation
- variable2 (v2): variable 2 for the frequency distribution and accumulation distribution calculation
- head (he): Reduce by the N most repeated values (mode) in variable 2

The following parameters are for configuring details about the visual charts plotted:

- stacked (s): if the bar chart is stacked or not
- yAxesName (yName): Name of the yAxesName. An informative parameter
- datasetName (dn): Name of the used dataset. An informative parameter
- name (n): Name of the visualization. An informative parameter
- description (des): Description of the visualization. An informative parameter

2.2.4.3 SKA-EDA 1^T PROTOTYPE INVOCATION

For this second release a standalone version of the SKA-EDA v1 has been provided. It is a python script and therefore in order to execute it, it is enough to call the following commands:

- Frequency distribution across one category: number of observations across the categories corresponding to the values of a categorical variable.

For this case we take as example one of the visualizations required by Use Case 3: number of road incidents (number of observations) by district. The policy maker is interested in getting the number of incidents of type “Road Infrastructure” for each of the different districts in the SOFIA city. The type of distribution, frequency distribution, is set by the “frequencyDistribution” parameter a true, the type of incident is set by the “datasetFolder” parameter, and the variable to be analyzed/plotted is set by the “-v1” parameter.

The following picture shows the invocation:

```
(pc-env) ~/policyCloud/exploratoryAnalysis$ python3 SKA_EDA_v0.1.py --useCase="uc3" --datasetFolder="/home/.../policyCloud/datasets/SOFIAUseCase/RoadInfrastructure/" --frequencyDistribution=True -v1=district
```

FIGURE 14 - SKA-EDA INVOCATION 1

Please refer to figure 20 - SKA-EDA_v1 results json file example1 for seeing the json outputs.

- Frequency distribution across several categories

For this case we take as example other visualizations required by Use Case 3: number of road incidents (number of observations) per month and per category. The particular use case is set by the “--useCase” parameter, the specific location of the dataset is set by the “--datasetFolder” parameter, the type of distribution, in that particular case frequency distribution, is setting the “frequencyDistribution” parameter a true, the type of incidents is set by the “datasetFolder” parameter, and the variables to group by are set through the “-v1” and “-v2” parameters.

The following picture shows the invocation:

```
(pc-env) ~/policyCloud/exploratoryAnalysis$ python3 SKA_EDA_v0.1.py --useCase="uc3" --datasetFolder="/home/ /policyCloud/datasets/SOFIAUseCase/RoadInfrastructure/" --frequencyDistribution=True -v1="monthYear" -v2="type_description" --stacked=True
```

FIGURE 15 - SKA-EDA INVOCATION 2

Please refer to figure 21 - SKA-EDA_v1 results json file example2 for seeing the json outputs.

- Accumulation of one variable across multiple categories

For this case, we take as an example the visualization required by Scenario 1 from Use Case 4: the accumulation of variable “Value” (number of claimants) across Gender and Year/Month. The particular use case is set by the --useCase parameter, the specific location of the dataset is set by the “--datasetFolder” parameter, the type of distribution, in that particular case the accumulation of a variable, is setting the “-ad” parameter (the reduced mode of “--accumulatedDistribution”) to true, and the variables to group by are set through the “-v1” and “-v2” parameters.

The following picture shows the invocation:

```
(pc-env) ~/policyCloud/exploratoryAnalysis$ python3 SKA_EDA_v0.1.py --useCase="uc4" --datasetFolder="/home/ /policyCloud/datasets/LONDONUseCase/" -ad=True -v1="monthYear" -v2="Gender Name" --stacked=False
```

FIGURE 16 - SKA-EDA INVOCATION 3

Please, refer to figure 22 - SKA-EDA_v1 results json file example3 for seeing the json outputs

- Geographical distribution

For this case we take as example another visualization required by Use Case 3: number of road incidents (number of observations) per geographical location. The particular use case is set by the --useCase parameter, the specific location of the dataset is set by the “--datasetFolder” parameter, the type of distribution, in that particular case the geographical distribution, is setting the “-gd” parameter (the reduced mode of “--geographicalDistribution”) to true, and the variable to group by is set through the “-v1” parameters.

The following picture shows the invocation:

```
(pc-env) :~/policyCloud/exploratoryAnalysis$ python3 SKA_EDA_v0.1.py --useCase="uc3"
--datasetFolder="/home/ /policyCloud/datasets/SOFIAUseCase/RoadInfrastructure/" -gd=True -v
l="district"
```

FIGURE 17 - SKA-EDA INVOCATION 4

Please refer to figure 23 - SKA-EDA_v1 results json file example4 for seeing the json outputs.

When no “--frequencyDistribution” or “--accumulatedDistribution” parameters are introduced, all distributions required for a concrete use case are performed. In particular:

- For Use Case 3, when the SKA-EDA v1 is executed just with --useCase="uc3" and --datasetFolder="/datasetFolder/" parameters, following distributions are computed:
 - frequency distribution of a single categorical variable: “subcategory”, “district”
 - frequency distribution for several categorical variables: “month and subcategory”, “month and district”, “subcategory and district”
 - location distribution: district
- For Use Case 4, when SKA-EDA v1 is executed just with --useCase="usc4" and --datasetFolder="/datasetFolder/" parameters, the following distributions are computed:
 - variable distribution across different categories: “monthYear and Gender Name”

Last, here are two samples of the datasets used for this second release:

- Road Infrastructure: 10 variables are used for this SKA-EDA v1 in the context of Use Case 3. For some of them, timestamp and location, a set of format transformations are applied to them. It is still under discussion whether or not a language translation task will be needed for the textual variables. The “type description” is a categorical variable. On the other hand, the translation of “description” only would have legibility purposes since no textual analysis is planned in the context of this use case.

category_id	type_id	type_description	signal_id	timestamp	description	location	status_id	street_number	district
0	5	154 Неправилно паркирали автомобили на пътно пла...	1943	2015-01-05 12:33:08.615	<r>След подмяна на тротоарната настилна на ул.&...	POINT (23.320380449295 42.7014769752565)	4	164	район Възраждане
1	5	85 Неправилно паркирали автомобили в зелени площи	1983	2015-01-07 10:47:03.841	<r>Здравейте, </r></p><r>От няколко години,...	POINT (23.3170947432518 42.6681002164685)	8	48Б	район Лозенец
2	5	85 Неправилно паркирали автомобили в зелени площи	1998	2015-01-07 17:57:49.810	<r>В зелената площ до пресечката на ул Христарк...	POINT (23.3530148863792 42.699643575855)	8	1	район Подуяне
3	5	85 Неправилно паркирали автомобили в зелени площи	2000	2015-01-07 18:01:14.218	<r>В зелената площ до пресечката на ул Христарк...	POINT (23.3552625775337 42.6997539632855)	8	11	район Подуяне
4	5	85 Неправилно паркирали автомобили в зелени площи	2001	2015-01-07 18:05:41.587	<r>В зелената площ пред блок 221Б в кв. Сухара...	POINT (23.3567029237747 42.7001966198383)	8	221Б Г	район Подуяне

FIGURE 18 - USE CASE 3 STRUCTURE SAMPLE

- JSA And UC Claimants in Camden: 3 variables (Date, Gender Name and Value) are used for this SKA-EDA v1 in the context of Use Case 4.

	Date	Geography Code	Geography Type	Gender Name	Age Name	Measure Name	Value	Unique Reference Number	Location	Last Uploaded
0	04/01/2013 12:00:00 AM	E01000907	2011 super output areas - lower layer	Total	All categories: Age 16+	Claimant count	60	Nm-162d1d32212e0d1249903482d0d0d1d20100	POINT (-0.1425054171560849 51.563955551457084)	02/12/2020 09:51:08 AM
1	04/01/2013 12:00:00 AM	E01000907	2011 super output areas - lower layer	Total	Age unknown (clerical claims)	Claimant count	0	Nm-162d1d32212e0d1249903482d0d0d1d20100	POINT (-0.1425054171560849 51.563955551457084)	02/12/2020 09:51:08 AM
2	04/01/2013 12:00:00 AM	E01000907	2011 super output areas - lower layer	Total	Aged 16-24	Claimant count	10	Nm-162d1d32212e0d1249903482d0d0d2d1d20100	POINT (-0.1425054171560849 51.563955551457084)	02/12/2020 09:51:08 AM
3	04/01/2013 12:00:00 AM	E01000907	2011 super output areas - lower layer	Total	Aged 25-49	Claimant count	40	Nm-162d1d32212e0d1249903482d0d0d3d1d20100	POINT (-0.1425054171560849 51.563955551457084)	02/12/2020 09:51:08 AM
4	04/01/2013 12:00:00 AM	E01000907	2011 super output areas - lower layer	Total	Aged 50+	Claimant count	10	Nm-162d1d32212e0d1249903482d0d0d4d1d20100	POINT (-0.1425054171560849 51.563955551457084)	02/12/2020 09:51:08 AM

FIGURE 19 - USE CASE 4 STRUCTURE SAMPLE

2.2.4.4 SKA-EDA 1^T PROTOTYPE OUTPUT

The SKA-EDA v1 analysis outputs a json file containing the categories to be depicted in a bar chart. It is a list of *categories/occurrences* objects where each of them has the following format:

- "stacked", true if the (bar) chart is shown stacked. By default it is false.
- "filterToUse":
- "filterValue":
- "x-axes": name of x-axes.
- "y-axes": name of y-axes.
- "name": name of the distributions shown.
- "description": brief description of the distributions shown.
- "startDate": the initial date of the period to be analysed
- "endDate": the end date of the period to be analysed. If the end date is null the analysis is performed for a concrete moment denoted by start date.
- "events", the required summaries of the data

The "events" element acquires different formats depending on the type of distributions:

- Frequency distribution across one category (see figure 20 - SKA-EDA_v1 results json file example1 for more details):
 - Events: a list of elements, where each element contains two elements:
 - key, a specific value (category) for variable 1
 - value, the occurrences of this value
- Frequency distribution across several categories and accumulation distributions (see figure 21 - SKA-EDA_v1 results json file example2, and figure 22 - SKA-EDA_v1 results json file example3 for more details)

- Events: a list of elements, where each element contains N elements:
 - specific value₁ (category₁) for variable 2: the occurrences of this value
 -
 - specific value_N (category_N) for variable 2: occurrences of this value
 - category: the variable1 value

As it can be seen, the result format is general enough to host the result of different types of aggregation related to one categorical variable. It will be a matter of replacing the variable 1 to make this SKA-EDA v1 analysis reusable for other different data sources/variables.

Below, an example of the output of the frequency distribution across one category can be seen.

```
{
  "stacked": false,
  "filterToUse": "",
  "filterValue": [],
  "x-axes": "district",
  "y-axes": "observations",
  "name": "frequency distribution across one (or several) categories",
  "description": "number of observations in Road Infrastructure per district",
  "startDate": "2020-01-01 00:00:00.000",
  "endDate": "2020-12-31 23:59:59.000",
  "n": {
    "description": "Reduce to the most N repeated values (modes) in ",
    "value": 3},
  "events": [
    {"key": "район Банкя", "values": 25},
    {"key": "район Витоша", "values": 571},
    {"key": "район Връбница", "values": 139}, ...
  ]
}
```

FIGURE 20 - SKA-EDA_V1 RESULTS JSON FILE EXAMPLE1

Below, an example of the output of the frequency distribution across several categories can be seen.

```
{
  "stacked": True,
  "filterToUse": "",
  "filterValue": [],
  "x-axes": "monthYear",
  "y-axes": "observations",
  "name": "frequency distribution across one (or several) categories",
  "description": "number of observations in Road Infrastructure per monthYear(x-axes) and per type_description(in colours)",
  "startDate": "2020-01-01 00:00:00.000",
  "endDate": "2020-12-31 23:59:59.000",
  "n": {
    "description": "Reduce to the most N repeated values (modes) in ",
    "value": 3},
  "events": [
    {
      "Липсващи или повредени стационарни антипаркинг стълбчета": 190,
      "Неправомерно поставяне върху тротоари на оградащи елементи": 122,
      "Счупени или липсващи капаци на шахти": 81,
      "category": "2020-01"},
    {"Липсващи или повредени стационарни антипаркинг стълбчета": 148,
      "Неправомерно поставяне върху тротоари на оградащи елементи": 98, "Счупени или липсващи капаци на шахти": 93, "category": "2020-02"}, ...]
  ]
}
```

FIGURE 21 - SKA-EDA_V1 RESULTS JSON FILE EXAMPLE2

Below, an example of the output of the accumulation of one variable across multiple categories can be seen.

```
{
  "stacked": false,
  "filterToUse": "",
  "filterValue": [],
  "x-axes": "monthYear",
  "y-axes": "claimants",
  "name": "distribution of Value (number of claimants) across multiples categories",
  "description": "number of claimants in JSA And UC Claimants In Camden per monthYear(x-axes) and per Gender Name(in colours)",
  "startDate": "2020-01-01 00:00:00.000",
  "endDate": "2020-12-31 23:59:59.000",
  "n": {
    "description": "Reduce to the most N repeated values (modes) in Gender Name",
    "value": 3
  },
  "events": [
    {"Female": 3435, "Male": 4725, "Total": 8260, "category": "2020-01"},
    {"Female": 3625, "Male": 4850, "Total": 8515, "category": "2020-02"},
    {"Female": 3645, "Male": 4885, "Total": 8690, "category": "2020-03"},
    {"Female": 6305, "Male": 8260, "Total": 14570, "category": "2020-04"},
    ...
  ]
}
```

FIGURE 22 - SKA-EDA_V1 RESULTS JSON FILE EXAMPLE3

The SKA-EDA v1 analysis, in the case of geographical distribution, outputs a json file containing a list of events that happened in the specific values of the geographical variable. See below the json description:

- "level": administrative divisions used for centering the map of the use case area of research (i.e.: country, city, ..)
- "name": name of the administrative division used for centering the map of the use case area of research (i.e: Bulgaria, Sofia, ..)
- "location": a GeoJson object which describes the use case area of research (i.e.: the GeoJson location of the Sofia city)
- "data" , a list of elements, each of them with the following fields:
 - "events", a list containing the events found in a particular value of the geographical variable (i.e: if the analysis is a geographical distribution of the variable "district", this list will contain the events that happen in each of the values of the variable "district", for example all the events that happen in "Повредена спирка" district). For each event following information is attached
 - "eventid": identifier of the event
 - "timestamp": 1582796185706,
 - "latitude": latitude where the event happens,
 - "longitude": longitude where the event happens
 - "year": year when the event happens
 - "month": month when the event happens
 - "day": day when the event happens
 - "esummary": description of the event
 - location2": a GeoJson object describing the location a specific value of the geographical variable (i.e: the GeoJson location of the "Повредена спирка" district).
 - num_events": number of events found in a particular value of the geographical variable (i.e: the total number of events found in the "Повредена спирка" district)
 - "startDate": the init date of the period to be analysed
 - "endDate": the end date of the period to be analysed. If the end date is null the analysis is performer for a concrete moment denoted by start date

Below, an example of the output of the geographical distribution can be seen.


```
{
  "level": "city",
  "name": "Sofia",
  "location": {"type": "Point", "coordinates": [23.329334, 42.719941]},
  "data":
  [
    {"events": [
      {"eventid": 194593,
        "timestamp": 1582796185706,
        "latitude": "42.7145446150652",
        "longitude": "23.1410249588608",
        "iyear": 2020,
        "imonth": 2,
        "iday": 27,
        "esummary": "Повредена спирка."},
      {"eventid": 223511,
        "timestamp": 1601374103001,
        "latitude": "42.7066619684188",
        "longitude": "23.1562459819193",
        "iyear": 2020,
        "imonth": 9,
        "iday": 29,
        "esummary": "Заградено пътно плат"},
      ...
    ],
    "location2": {"region_txt": "район Банкя", "region": 1},
    "num_events": 25, "startDate": "2020-01-01 00:00:00.000",
    "endDate": "2020-12-31 23:59:59.000"},
    {"events": [
      {"eventid": 187286,
        "timestamp": 1578047199340,
        "latitude": "42.6414943744128",
        "longitude": "23.2938613793457",
        "iyear": 2020,
        "imonth": 1,
        "iday": 3,
        "esummary": "Запазват се места."},
      {"eventid": 187324,
        "timestamp": 1578060333283,
        "latitude": "42.6528811953623",
        "longitude": "23.2632676652902",
        "iyear": 2020,
        "imonth": 1,
        "iday": 3,
        "esummary": "Саксии на пътя, коит"},
      ...
    ],
    "location2": {"region_txt": "район Трианица", "region": 24},
    "num_events": 686,
    "startDate": "2020-01-01 00:00:00.000",
    "endDate": "2020-12-31 23:59:59.000"
  ]
},
  "id": 2,
  "typeOfCharts": "HEATMAP_POI"}
```

FIGURE 23 - SKA-EDA_V1 RESULTS JSON FILE EXAMPLE

Future versions of the SKA-EDA will be focused on:

- storing the results in the PolicyCLOUD storage from where the PDT backend will retrieve the results and make them available to the PDT.
- make the prototype deployable via Docker [38] and OpenWhisk [8].
- including future functionality in the field of exploring the datasets

2.2.5 Opinion Mining & Sentiment Analysis

2.2.5.1 SUMMARY OF CHANGES: OPINION MINING & SENTIMENT ANALYSIS

The previous version of the sentiment, reported in the 1st prototype (D4.2) was a document-level sentiment based on Vader [46] and Textblob [47]. For this second prototype a new version of the sentiment is about to be released. This new version is an entity-level sentiment based on deep learning approach (such BERT).

2.2.5.2 FIRST EXPERIMENT WITH ENTITY-LEVEL SENTIMENT ANALYSIS

In the context of this first experiment concerning the task of the Entity-level Sentiment Analysis (ELSA) the initial pipeline and workflow of this task has been identified and is being depicted in the below figure.

FIGURE 24 - BERT-BASED ENTITY LEVEL SENTIMENT ANALYSIS (BERT-BASED ELSA)

As presented in the above figure several components from WP3 and WP4 of the PolicyCLOUD project are being utilized and integrated to perform this task.

The first component that also initializes the overall process is the Cloud Gateways component, which through the utilization of its Twitter Microservice, introduced in D3.5, provides access to Twitter data to the overall PolicyCLOUD platform throughout the usage and initialization of the Twitter API v0.2.

Afterwards, the Data Cleaning component is responsible to perform the initial and necessary data pre-processing and cleaning on the collected tweets. Data obtained from twitter usually contains a lot of

HTML entities, links, username, punctuations, emojis, hashtags etc., which get embedded in the original data. Thus, it is necessary to filter and delete all these entities.

What is more, as the overall process deals with raw text several NLP subtasks should be utilized to extract value and knowledge out of the raw tweets. To this end, two specific subtasks are being utilized. The BERT-based contextual Word Embedding and the Named Entity Recognition (NER). Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT) [43] approach has been selected as the backbone of the above-presented pipeline and workflow as it is a pre-trained bidirectional Transformer encoder that achieves state-of-the-art performances across a variety of NLP tasks [44], [45]. Hence, the word embedding subtask is implemented through the utilization of BERT as it introduces a context-aware word embedding layer pre-trained on large-scale datasets. On top of this, the subtask of NER is also utilized to extract and classify named entities found in the tweets, as introduced and analyzed in Section 2.1.2.2 of this deliverable.

The 4th step in the above-presented architecture is the component of the Enhanced Interoperability, which is responsible for the final annotation of the initial tweets with the already identified entities as also with the appropriate topics in which the tweet has been classified through the Topic Identification subtask.

Finally, the BERT-based Sentiment Analysis task is implemented. Under the scopes of this first prototype a ready-to-use Python library is utilized, the aspect-based-sentiment-analysis². The latter bases its functionality directly to BERT's next-sentence prediction to formulate the task as a sequence-pair classification.

² <https://pypi.org/project/aspect-based-sentiment-analysis/>

```
In [280]: text3 = "Carriřena wine is a must taste kind of wine. In contrary to Merlot which is not as tasty as Carriřena"

import aspect_based_sentiment_analysis as absa

recognizer = absa.aux_models.BasicPatternRecognizer()
nlp = absa.load(pattern_recognizer=recognizer)
completed_task = nlp(text3, aspects=["Merlot","Carriřena"])
Merlot, Carriřena = completed_task.examples

absa.summary(Carriřena)
absa.display(Carriřena.review)

Sentiment.positive for "Carriřena"
Scores (neutral/negative/positive): [0.062 0.057 0.88 ]

Importance 1.00 carriřena wine is a must taste kind of wine . in contrary to merlot which is not as tasty as carriřena
Importance 1.00 carriřena wine is a must taste kind of wine . in contrary to merlot which is not as tasty as carriřena
Importance 0.79 carriřena wine is a must taste kind of wine . in contrary to merlot which is not as tasty as carriřena
Importance 0.70 carriřena wine is a must taste kind of wine . in contrary to merlot which is not as tasty as carriřena
Importance 0.50 carriřena wine is a must taste kind of wine . in contrary to merlot which is not as tasty as carriřena

In [281]: absa.summary(Merlot)
absa.display(Merlot.review)

Sentiment.negative for "Merlot"
Scores (neutral/negative/positive): [0.127 0.559 0.314]

Importance 1.00 carriřena wine is a must taste kind of wine . in contrary to merlot which is not as tasty as carriřena
Importance 0.52 carriřena wine is a must taste kind of wine . in contrary to merlot which is not as tasty as carriřena
Importance 0.40 carriřena wine is a must taste kind of wine . in contrary to merlot which is not as tasty as carriřena
Importance 0.37 carriřena wine is a must taste kind of wine . in contrary to merlot which is not as tasty as carriřena
Importance 0.33 carriřena wine is a must taste kind of wine . in contrary to merlot which is not as tasty as carriřena
```

FIGURE 25 - "ELSA FIRST EXPERIMENT OUTCOMES"

As presented in the above figure, the first conducted experiments and their outcomes through the utilization of this Python library have shown remarkable results. Both defined wine entities, the Carinena and the Merlot, have been identified well and their sentiments have been extracted in high accuracy by the utilized model.

More experiments will be conducted as the project evolves and a more project-based solution will be introduced during the next months.

2.2.5.3 INTEGRATION OF ENTITY-LEVEL SENTIMENT ANALYSIS IN POLICYCLOUD

As it has been commented in previous sections, the entity-level sentiment analysis is built using the same approach as the document-based sentiment analysis release in the first prototype. Therefore, some of the components required for this second version of the sentiment analysis system are already developed, some others have been updated towards a PolicyCLOUD-integrated version and some others are completely new. Let's summarize them:

- Ingest Function Component: For the ingest function to generate the sentiment of the tweets. This component was built on top of Apache NiFi and basically it consists of an Apache NiFi workflow connected to Kafka topics for getting inputs and putting outputs. It includes some parameters that need to be filled: the connection to the Apache NiFi instance, the connections with the Kafka topics, and the microservice endpoint. This component for the ingest function was developed for the previous release and is fully documented and presented in D4.2.

- **Aggregate function component:** The aggregate function to generate some aggregates, it is connected at the start and at the end with the PolicyCLOUD Datastore. Another Apache Nifi workflow was developed for getting the data from the PolicyCLOUD Datastore (tweets + sentiment tags sent to Kafka in the ingest function) and storing the aggregated results back again in the PolicyCLOUD Datastore. It implies a set of parameters such as: datastore endpoint, and other important parameters that define how to aggregate are: start date, end date and periodicity. This component has been updated with respect to the last release, where the data were extracted from local files and not from the PolicyCLOUD Datastore, but it can be found in a very detailed description in D4.2 as well.
- **Entity-level sentiment analysis microservice.** This new component will contain the logic of the new entity-level sentiment analysis. It is a new component that is deployed as a microservice, using Python and Flask, and it is still under construction at the closure of this document. More details on the approach followed by the entity-level sentiment analysis provided by this microservice can be found in the “TRADITIONAL MACHINE LEARNING APPROACHES VS DEEP/LEARNING APPROACHES” SECTION.

The schema data output by the ingest function, the JSON object that will contain the id and created at fields with the sentiment information extracted from the entity-level sentiment analysis, is still under discussion.

2.2.6 Social Dynamics & Behavioural Data Analytics

2.2.6.1 SUMMARY OF CHANGES: SOCIAL DYNAMICS AND BEHAVIOURAL DATA ANALYTICS

Previously the Social Dynamics module supported the development, simulation and analysis of policy models in isolation. Now this module has been transformed into a more general framework for supporting policy design that allows the specification, simulation and comparison of multiple policy alternatives. To this end we have developed novel, graphical user interfaces for the development and execution of meta-simulation structures that (i) describe and apply various modelling assumptions on the simulation of multiple policy alternatives, (ii) allow the specification of various criteria for comparing the simulation results of various policy alternatives, and (iii) provide 2D and 3D graph visualizations of the social network that results from each simulation cycle.

2.2.6.2 USER INTERFACES FOR SOCIAL DYNAMICS & BEHAVIOURAL DATA ANALYTICS

We describe the options available to the user for interacting with the latest version of Politika and provide relevant screenshots.

The main screen of the system lists the existing policy/simulation models in the system and allows the user to create a new policy/simulation model. Existing policies and simulations are listed either as Public meaning that their author has given editing permissions to all users or as My Policies/Simulations meaning that they have been created by the logged-in user.

FIGURE 26 – POLITIKA INTRO SCREEN WITH OPTIONS TO LIST EXISTING POLICIES/SIMULATIONS OR TO CREATE NEW ONES

Clicking on New Simulation the user is presented with a form for creating a new simulation. The form contains a set of text boxes that the user needs to fill. After submitting the form, it is checked for syntactic correctness of the various fields. If all fields are correct a new simulation is created in the database, otherwise the system displays the same form as filled by the user and containing a list of messages describing the errors messages that were spotted in the user input.

Selecting any of the listed simulations the user is able to inspect the simulation parameters. A top menu allows him to edit these parameters, run the simulation, examine its results, delete the simulation or perform analysis of these results,

The Edit option extends the form described for the New simulation option with the additional options to:

- upload social network data from a user-supplied text file in JSON format using the Input Network field
- create synthetic data for a social network automatically by the system using the New radio button. In this case the user needs to specify the size of the social network (the number of nodes in the graph) and the Generator parameters that will be used for generating the network.

Edit Base case for Radicalization

Title

Base case for Radicalization

Description

Explores what may happen to a social group when radicalization is left unchecked

Public?

Private?

Policy related parameters

radicals: 0, sympathizers: 0, conformists: 0, radicalization_threshold: 0.5, conformism_threshold: 0, friendship_threshold: 0

Individual attributes

radicalization_status: rand_float(-1, 1), x: rand_int(-200, 200), y: rand_int(-200, 200), z: rand_int(1, 5), red: rand_int(0, 255), green: rand_int(0, 255), blue: rand_int(0, 255), alpha: 0.75, radius: 10, scale: 1

Connection attributes

contact_strength: rand_float(-1, 1), influence: 0, red: rand_int(0, 255), green: rand_int(0, 255), blue: rand_int(0, 255)

Policy related dynamics

```
IF true DO this.radicals: global_count("this.radicalization_status >
global.radicalization_threshold", population)/size; this.sympathizers:
global_count("this.radicalization_status > global.conformism_threshold and
this.radicalization_status < global.radicalization_threshold", population)/size;
```

Node dynamics

```
IF true DO this.radicalization_status: this.radicalization_status + sum_in(this.state,
"edge.influence") ~ IF this.radicalization_status < -1 DO this.radicalization_status: -1
~ IF this.radicalization_status > 1 DO this.radicalization_status: 1 ~ IF true DO this.x:
this.x + 2 * (this.radicalization_status * this.y - this.x * this.radicalization_status
```

Connection dynamics

```
IF true DO edge.influence: this.radicalization_status * edge.contact_strength
```


The screenshot shows the lower portion of a web form for editing a simulation. It features several sections separated by horizontal lines:

- New network**: A radio button is selected.
- Size**: A text input field containing the number "50".
- Generator**: A text area containing the JSON configuration: `max_edges: 5, min_edges: 1, directed?: false, degree_distribution: :homogeneous`.
- Use existing network**: A radio button is unselected.
- Import network**: A file upload section with a "Choose File" button and the text "No file chosen".
- Cycles**: A text input field containing the number "10".
- Sampling period**: A text input field containing the number "1".

At the bottom of the form is a blue "SUBMIT" button.

FIGURE 27 - EDITING FORM FOR A SIMULATION IN POLITIKA (UPPER AND LOWER PARTS)

The Delete option allows the user to delete a specific simulation from Politika after the user confirms this choice through a confirmation window displayed on the screen.

The Results option shows a list of nodes and their resulting attributes for each node in the social network after the simulation has finished. The details of each node are displayed in raw text form.

Scaled Node Attributes for Radicalization Demo

The horizontal axis lists all nodes. Attribute values are shown as equal-width rectangles linearly scaled from a domain of their min and max values to a height between 0 and 1 on the vertical axis. Moving the cursor on top of a rectangle, shows the value of its corresponding attribute.

FIGURE 30 - EXAMPLE SCREEN DEPICTING THE ATTRIBUTE VALUES FOR EACH NODE IN A SIMULATED SOCIAL NETWORK

Clicking on New Policy the user is presented with a form for creating a new policy. The form contains a set of text boxes that the user needs to fill. After submitting the form, it is checked for syntactic correctness of the various fields. If all fields are correct, a new screen with a GUI for specifying a new policy is created, otherwise the system displays the same form as filled by the user and containing a list of messages describing the errors messages that were spotted in the user input.

Selecting any of the listed policies the user is able to inspect the policy parameters. A top menu allows him to clone this policy, edit its parameters through a GUI or delete the policy.

Politika provides a GUI on the web that allows the designer to create/edit a tree representation of a policy as described in the previous sections. Figure 31 provides a screenshot of this GUI corresponding to the radicalization policy example. The user can click on the tree nodes depicted and examine, edit, delete or execute the clicked node. Executing a node means that the system propagates all design parameters defined on the path from the clicked node to the root to all the nodes belonging to the subtree with the clicked node as root. In addition, the system then automatically creates a bottom-up processing pipeline from all the nodes in this subtree to the clicked node.

FIGURE 31 - SCREENSHOT OF THE POLITIKA GUI FOR MANAGING POLICY HIERARCHIES

In the preceding figure, green, orange, blue and yellow nodes respectively depict policies, goals, objectives and step nodes.

Furthermore, following Figure 32 provides a snapshot of a web-based GUI for visualizing and editing the population network used in policy design either in 2D or 3D. The visualizer uses a number of attributes for each node related to visualization (x, y, z, red, green, blue, alpha, radius, scale). As the figure indicates, the user can click on a node in the graph and examine/edit the attributes of the individual corresponding to this node. Furthermore, he can insert/delete nodes/edges in the graph, mainly to fine-tune the population that was generated by the network generation component. Finally, the GUI allows the user to visualize the execution of a social dynamics simulation on the network.

FIGURE 32 - SCREENSHOT OF THE POLITIKA GUI FOR MANAGING NETWORK DATA AND VISUALIZING THE EXECUTION OF SIMULATIONS ON THE POPULATION NETWORK

Demo and Current System Version

A demo video of the current version of Politika is available at (<https://youtu.be/1lg3FtncyFM>), while an experimental version of the system resides in (epinoetic.org:4000).

2.2.7 Operational Data Repository

2.2.7.1 SUMMARY OF CHANGES: OPERATIONAL DATA REPOSITORY

During the second period of the project, focus was given on the implementation of the Java direct API of the operational data repository, which allows direct data connections to the storage engine without the need to interact with the relational query engine. This reduces the software footprint of the latter, boosts the performance by achieving better response time and increases the throughput of parallel operations that can be performed concurrently. Therefore, the following subsection has been enhanced with details about the use of this new delivered API.

2.2.7.2 OPERATIONAL DATA REPOSITORY: INTERFACE DOCUMENTATION

The operational data repository provides various interfaces for data connectivity that can be used in different scenarios. Firstly, it implements the JDBC interface, which is a standard specified under the Java JSR-221³. JDBC allows for a connection with the SQL query engine of the operational data repository, where the data user can exploit the SQL query language in order to perform complex query statements supported by the rich capabilities of the SQL itself. Currently, the JDBC driver of the operational datastore supports the execution of the standard SQL statements, under its current ISO SQL:2016.

In addition to JDBC, an implementation of the OData⁴ specification has been provided, which is an OASIS standard that allows the connection to a data store via well-defined REST API. It allows for the integration of components incompatible with JDBC and cannot usually open direct connections to a datastore, rather than should communicate via HTTP messages.

Moreover, the operational data repository provides a direct API that allows to directly open connections to the storage engine of LXS. The latter provide rich query capabilities like SQL; however, it cannot support JOIN operations. The benefit of directly connecting to the storage is that both data connections and query executions are performed much more efficiently, as direct connection permits to bypass the query engine layer. This is crucial in cases where very low latency is a requirement, such as to support data ingestion at very high rates. In this second phase of the project, this direct API has been released, written in Java and packaged as a library into a Jar file. It contains the JNI binding that allows Java code to invoke native code written in C. The interface is similar to the ones used by popular document-based datastores, such as MongoDB.

In order to connect, the application developer has to firstly open a *session* providing the details for data connectivity, such as the URL and port of the datastore, the logical database name and user specific credentials as the following code snippet depicts:

```
Settings settings = Settings.parse("lx://lxserver:9876/db@APP");
```

```
// you can overwrite any connection property
```

³ <https://jcp.org/en/jsr/detail?id=221>

⁴ <https://www.odata.org/documentation/>

```
settings.add("URL", "kivi:ixis://lxserver:9876");
settings.add("DATABASE", "db");
settings.add("USER", user);
```

```
Session session = SessionFactory.newSession(settings);
Database database = session.database();
```

The application developer needs to first define the *settings* of the connection, thus the connection URL, username etc, and then to create a new *session* from which it can request the logical database to perform operations upon. Once the *database* object has been created, the application developer can use it to get access to specific data tables, and insert new records to it. This happens by defining the data item to be inserted, the *tuple*, and inserting the latter to the database, as the following code snippet indicates:

```
Table people = database.getTable("person");
Tuple person = people.createTuple();
```

```
//Fill in tuple fields
```

```
person.put("id", 1L)
    .put("name", "John")
    .put("lastName", "Doe")
    .put("phone", "555333695")
    .put("email", "johndoe@nowhere.no")
    .put("birthday", Date.valueOf("1970-01-01"))
    .put("numChildren", 4);
```

```
//Insert tuple
```

```
people.insert(person);
```

```
//Tuples are sent to the datastore when COMMIT is done
```

```
session.commit();
```

In cases of an auto-incremented primary key field, the application developer must define a *sequence*. Using the *sequence*, it can get the next auto-incremented value and set it as the primary key of the new record that needs to be inserted. As a result, the code snippet above should be slightly changed to rely on the retrieved value of the *sequence*:

```
long personId = database.getSequence("personId").nextVal();
```

```
person.put("id", personId, Long.class )
    .put("name", "John", String.class )
    .put("lastName", "Doe", String.class )
```

```
.put("phone", "555333695", String.class )
.put("email", "johndoe@nowhere.no", String.class )
.put("birthday", Date.valueOf("1970-01-01"), String.class )
.put("numChildren", 4, String.class );
```

Finally, when binary objects need to be stored, as in the case of the PDT backend, then the BLOB column must use an output stream Java operator to write the byte array, as follows:

```
person.put("name", "John")
    .put("lastName", "Doe")
    .put("phone", "555333695");
```

```
OutputStream os = people.createBlob(person, "photo");
Files.copy(Paths.get("/path/to/john.jpeg"), os);
```

For updating/deleting records, first the identifier record that needs to be updated/deleted must be defined using the *TupleKey* object. Then, the corresponding methods of the *table* class should be invoked accordingly, as the following code snippet illustrates:

```
// Tuple person to be updated has to be previously retrieved through
// a get()
```

```
Tuplekey key = table.createTupleKey();
key.put("id", 0L, Long.class );
```

```
Tuple person = table.get(key);
person.put("phone", "anotherPhone", String.class )
    .put("email", "johndoe@somewhere.some", String.class )
```

```
people.update(person);
```

```
//or delete this record
```

```
Table people = database.getTable("person");
TupleKey johnKey = people.createTupleKey();
johnKey.put("id", key);
people.delete(johnKey);
```

Finally, reading data can either be done via a get operation over the identifier, or by using a scan operation. For fetching data using a get, the application developer should use a code similar to the following snippet:

```
Tuplekey key = table.createTupleKey();
key.put("id", 0L, Long.class );
```

```
Tuple tuple = table.get(key);
```

In this example, again we need to define the corresponding *TupleKey* object and read it using its corresponding *get* operation. However, in cases we want to perform a *scan*, the above code must be changed to the following:

```
Table people = database.getTable("person");
TupleKey min = people.createTupleKey();
min.put("id", 20);
```

```
TupleKey max = people.createTupleKey();
max.put("id", 30L);
```

```
people.find()
    .min(min)
    .max(max)
    .forEach(tuple->processTuple(tuple));
```

```
// Max 20 results
```

```
people.find()
    .first(20)
    .forEach(tuple->processTuple(tuple));
```

In this example, a scan is defined over the primary key of the data table, as the application developer needs to define the upper and lower limit of the dataset to be scanned. Then, the *find* method needs to be invoked, that returns a Java *Iterator*. Using the latter, the application developer can now iterate through the returned data items using the *foreach* clause of Java.

In cases the user needs to scan over columns not defined having primary or secondary indexes, then a *filter* condition must be applied to the *find* method, as the following code snippets depict:

```
Table people = database.getTable("person");
```

```
// Basic comparisons
```

```
people.find()
    .filter(gt("numChildren", 4).and(eq("name", string("John"))))
    .forEach(tuple->processTuple(tuple));
```

```
// Between
```

```
Date minDate = Date.valueOf("1900-01-01");
Date maxDate = Date.valueOf("2000-01-01");
```

```
people.find()
    .filter(between("birthday", date(minDate), date(maxDate)))
    .forEach(tuple->processTuple(tuple));
```

// Using a Expression with operators

```
people.find()
    .filter(gt("numChildren",sub(field("numRooms"),int(1))))
    .forEach(tuple->processTuple(tuple));
```

In cases the application developer prefers to retrieve a specific list of columns, instead of the whole data item, he or she needs to perform a *projection* over the returned dataset. This can be also defined in the *find* method, as the following code snippet indicates.

```
String[] fields = {"name", "lastName", "birthDay"};
people.find()
    .project(include(fields))
    .forEach(tuple->{
        String name = tuple.get("name", String.class );
        String lastname = tuple.get("lastName", String.class );
        Date date = tuple.get("birthDay", Date.class );
    });

// SELECT name, Lastname, weight/height^2 AS imc FROM person
// Alias and expression usage

ProjectionExpression[] projExp = {
    alias("name"),
    alias("lastName")
};

people.find()
    .project(compose(projExp))
    .forEach(tuple->{
        String name = tuple.get("name", String.class );
        String lastName = tuple.get("lastName", String.class );
    });
```

Finally, the direct API can perform aggregate operations over the data tables. The application developer must define an initial array with the fields to be used as the group by the key (if any), and then a list of aggregation expressions over some fields. This is illustrated in the following code snippet:

```
// SELECT name, department, salary, sum(salary) OVER (PARTITION BY department) AS totalSalary
// FROM employees

employees.find()
.project(include("employee", "dept", "salary").addWindow(window("dept").sum("totalSalary", "salary")))
.forEach(tuple->{
Long employee = tuple.get("employee", Long.class );
String department = tuple.get("dept", String.class );
Long salary = tuple.get("salary", Long.class );
Long departmentSalary = tuple.get("totalSalary", Long.class );
});
// SELECT name, department, salary, sum(salary) OVER (PARTITION BY department ORDER BY salary) AS
totalSalary
// FROM employees

employees.find()
.project(include("employee", "dept", "salary").addWindow(window("dept").sum("totalSalary", "salary").orderBy("salary")))
.forEach(tuple->{
Long employee = tuple.get("employee", Long.class );
String department = tuple.get("dept", String.class );
Long salary = tuple.get("salary", Long.class );
Long departmentSalary = tuple.get("totalSalary", Long.class );
});

// SELECT name, department, salary, max(salary) OVER (PARTITION BY department)
// AS maxSalary FROM employees

employees.find()
.project(include("employee", "dept", "salary").addWindow(window("dept").max("maxSalary", "salary")))
.forEach(tuple->{
Long employee = tuple.get("employee", Long.class );
String department = tuple.get("dept", String.class );
Long salary = tuple.get("salary", Long.class );
Long maxSalary = tuple.get("maxSalary", Long.class );
});
```

```
// SELECT name, department, salary, min(salary) OVER (PARTITION BY department)
// AS minSalary FROM employees

employees.find()
.project(include("employee", "dept", "salary").addWindow(window("dept").min("minSalary", "salary")))
.forEach(tuple->{
Long employee = tuple.get("employee", Long.class );
String department = tuple.get("dept", String.class );
Long salary = tuple.get("salary", Long.class );
Long minSalary = tuple.get("minSalary", Long.class );
});

// SELECT name, department, salary, count(salary) OVER (PARTITION BY department)
// AS countSalary FROM employees

employees.find()
.project(include("employee", "dept", "salary").addWindow(window("dept").count("countSalary",
"salary")))
.forEach(tuple->{
Long employee = tuple.get("employee", Long.class );
String department = tuple.get("dept", String.class );
Long salary = tuple.get("salary", Long.class );
Long departmentSalary = tuple.get("countSalary", Long.class );
});

// SELECT name, department, salary, avg(salary) OVER (PARTITION BY department)
// AS avgSalary FROM employees

employees.find()
.project(include("employee", "dept", "salary").addWindow(window("dept").avg("avgSalary", "salary")))
.forEach(tuple->{
Long employee = tuple.get("employee", Long.class );
String department = tuple.get("dept", String.class );
Long salary = tuple.get("salary", Long.class );
double departmentSalary = tuple.get("avgSalary", Double.class );
});
```

Having the direct API released, now the data scientist can exploit the benefits of the direct connection to the storage and the lower latency of the query execution, using the already implemented connectors to popular data/streaming processing frameworks, such as Apache Spark and Apache Flink. Due to this, the data scientist can use the API of those frameworks, and those will make use of the direct API, through the connectors implemented and provided by the operational datastore.

2.3 Baseline technologies and tools

This section describes the baseline technologies and tools under the delivered components.

2.3.1 DAA API Gateway

2.3.1.1 KUBERNETES

Kubernetes [6] is the leading open-source container management platform used in production of growing number of enterprises as the base of private on-prem cloud, as well as offered by almost all cloud providers as a managed dedicated cluster, and as described in D4.3 [34] it is the chosen underlying platform for all PolicyCLOUD components. The underlying software components of DAA, both OpenWhisk and Kafka, have been deployed on a Kubernetes cluster over the PolicyCLOUD testbed h.

2.3.1.2 KAFKA

Apache Kafka [7] is used as a transformation buffer to store intermediate data between components in a reliable and asynchronous way. As in SW2, communication between functions is done through OpenWhisk, in the future in case the OpenWhisk limitations of input and output size (1MB) to actions would not be adequate, Kafka will be used as the intermediate buffering between functions as well.

The LeanXcale database interface has been implemented in the components integration phase using Kafka connector to insert the PolicyCLOUD processed datasets into the LeanXcale database backend (h).

2.3.1.3 OPENWHISK

Apache OpenWhisk [8] is an open source lightweight serverless platform that provides capability to deploy functions (written in any language) and specify triggers and rules by which the functions are executed. It offers a simple programming model where the function developer can concentrate only on the mere logic of the function, while the deployment and activation details are taken care of transparently. It is based on containers as the functions' wrapper and deploys and integrates perfectly in a Kubernetes environment. All analytic functions in PolicyCLOUD will be deployed as OpenWhisk actions, with appropriate triggers and activation rules, addressing the extensibility and reusability requirements. Additional important capability of OpenWhisk is the composition of functions to be activated per trigger/rule, which enable to specify a pipeline of analytic functions to be applied to a data source.

The DAA APIs are implemented as a set of serverless functions (in the OpenWhisk cluster), web actions were written to expose functions and data sources APIs with REST, implemented in node.js

Packages and package-bindings were implemented to store metadata and pass it as parameters in functions invocations.

Triggers, rules, and Kafka feed were used to subscribe to topics and apply data transformation functions as data enters the platform and is available.

Analytic functions are implemented using OpenWhisk actions. Sample reference functions were written in java and packaged in jar according to OpenWhisk actions guidelines and implement the connectivity to the LeanXcale database as backend.

2.3.1.4 GITLAB AND CONTAINER REGISTRY

Used to store project's WP4 DAA files, reference implementation and image container registry.

2.3.1.5 LOGSTASH

A centralized logging for PolicyCLOUD was implemented with a standard logging service by deploying logstash [35], arguably the most popular open-source log management tool, on PolicyCLOUD's Kubernetes infrastructure. The logging service is accessible to all PolicyCLOUD WPs using an HTTP API, and forms a centralized, project-wide infrastructure component. Each logging event is stored in a persistent file system enabled by NFS and ensures resiliency to pod failures and restarts.

2.3.2 Enhanced Interoperability & Data Cleaning

2.3.2.1 DATA CLEANING COMPONENT

The Data Cleaning component is developed with Python 3.7 using the Flask python micro web framework⁵. Flask is a powerful framework written in Python and based on the Werkzeug⁶ toolkit and Jinja2⁷ template engine that is independent from particular libraries or tools and that supports a large list of extensions for application features. Besides the Flask framework, a list of libraries and tools has been used in the context of the Data Cleaning to support several functionalities of the component. For the data structure handling Pandas⁸ has been selected, NumPy⁹ is used for all the numerical computations, while for the streaming data diverse nlp libraries and tools have been exploited (e.g., spacy).

2.3.2.2 ENHANCED INTEROPERABILITY COMPONENT

For the implementation and utilization of the first sub-component of the Enhanced Interoperability component, different technologies and techniques from the fields of NLP and Semantic Web were utilized. To this end, the overall code was implemented based on Python3 [9] programming language. Moreover, spaCy [10] framework was utilized to perform concrete and high accuracy NLP sub-tasks, such as Tokenization, Sentence splitting, POS tagging, NER etc., which are core tasks in the provided sub-component and their importance and overall functionality have introduced in previous sections. On top of this, NLP tasks integrate with Semantic Web technologies in order to provide a hybrid approach through the utilization of state-of-the-art SemAI mechanism. To this end, SPARQL [11], a widely used RDF query language, is being utilized. The latter is being used to perform queries on Wikidata Knowledge base to identify and interlink appropriate entities based on the ones that have already been recognised from

⁵ Flask, <http://flask.pocoo.org/>

⁶ Werkzeug, <http://werkzeug.pocoo.org/>

⁷ Jinja2, <http://jinja.pocoo.org/>

⁸ Pandas, <https://pandas.pydata.org/>

⁹ NumPy, <http://www.numpy.org/>

the raw texts. Moreover, the gensim¹⁰ library is being utilized under the scopes of the Topic Identification subtasks in order to provide the three (3) models for this specific task. Finally, the Neo4j¹¹ graph database is being used in the Ontology Mapping subtask in order to provide to the system the ability to store the semantic annotations and relationships of the provided data.

2.3.3 Situational Knowledge Acquisition & Analysis

As it has been described in the previous section, this component has been built using Python and well-known data analysis libraries such as Pandas [37].

2.3.4 Opinion Mining & Sentiment Analysis

This component is built as a data workflow using Apache NiFi, a powerful tool that allows us to create reusable modules and use them in data workflows in an easy way. In collaboration with Apache NiFi Registry to maintain the versions of the workflows developed, and to ease the process of exporting and importing the workflows in an automated way.

To execute the Apache NiFi workflows in an automated way without the GUI, the Python client SDK NiPyApi¹² are used. This client permits to connect to different Apache NiFi instances, export and import workflows, execute, and configure those workflows, and get the status of them, among others.

For the entity-level sentiment analysis function, some approaches/tools are being investigated to perform the sentiment of the tweets at entity-level. More information on the approaches that are being considered, please refer to “TRADITIONAL MACHINE LEARNING APPROACHES VS DEEP/LEARNING APPROACHES” section.

2.3.5 Social Dynamics & Behavioural Data Analytics

Politika has been implemented using the following baseline technologies:

- Elixir/Erlang (<https://elixir-lang.org/>)
- Phoenix Web Framework (<https://www.phoenixframework.org/>)
- D3.js (<https://d3js.org/>)

2.3.6 Operational Data Repository

The operational data repository consists of various components and tools, each one built over different baseline technologies and tools. More precisely, it consists of:

- The adaptable and distributed storage engine: It has been written in C and provides the capabilities for persistent storage of data elements.

¹⁰ Gensim, <https://radimrehurek.com/gensim/>

¹¹ Neo4j, <https://neo4j.com/>

¹² <https://nipyapi.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html>

- The transactional processing mechanism: It enables support for transactions and ensures ACID properties. It can be scaled out linearly and it has been completely implemented in Java 8.
- The query engine: It provides support for executing queries written in SQL scripting language. It has been implemented in Java 8 and makes use of the Apache Calcite query processing framework, which lies in its core and extends its functionality to provide fully SQL support.
- The monitoring engine: It makes use of the Prometheus monitoring framework for gathering metrics and monitoring information by each of its components. All components expose monitoring information to specific URIs where custom exporters are placing data that can be imported by Prometheus. Additionally, the openwizard.io framework is being used for exporting custom monitoring information (i.e. query compilation time) via JMX extensions.
- The monitoring dashboard: It makes use of the Grafana Dashboard for visualizing the monitoring information gathered by Prometheus.
- Ansible: An ansible installer is provided that automatically installs various components in a target infrastructure (either a virtual one via the use of containers, or over bare metal)

3. Source code

3.1 Availability

This section provides the links and access information to the actual code repositories.

3.1.1 DAA API Gateway

Software prototype code can be found on the PolicyCLOUD's github which is accessible to the members of the consortium and includes DAA code to deploy in OpenWhisk.

Gitlab: <https://registry.grid.ece.ntua.gr/oshrit/daa/>

Container registry: https://registry.grid.ece.ntua.gr/oshrit/daa/container_registry

3.1.2 Enhanced Interoperability & Data Cleaning

3.1.2.1 DATA CLEANING COMPONENT

The software prototype of the Data Cleaning is provided in PolicyCLOUD's GitLab repository and can be found under the URL:

<https://registry.grid.ece.ntua.gr/george/cleaninginteroperability>

3.1.2.2 ENHANCED INTEROPERABILITY COMPONENT

Software prototype code can be found on the PolicyCLOUD's Gitlab repository, which is accessible to the members of the consortium, under the URL below:

<https://registry.grid.ece.ntua.gr/george/cleaninginteroperability>

3.1.3 Situational Knowledge Acquisition & Analysis

The code is available at: <https://registry.grid.ece.ntua.gr/maria.sanguino/exploratoryanalysis> and has the following folder structure:

- SKA_EDA_v0.1.py ☐ it contains all the source code of the prototype.

3.1.4 Opinion Mining & Sentiment Analysis

The code is available at <http://snf-877903.vm.oceanos.grnet.gr/jorge/sentimentanalysis> and has the next folder structure:

- **Root:** description of the git project and details in the requirements and steps needed to deploy it.

- **Functions:** folder that contains the python code to execute the sentiment and the aggregate functions.
 - nifi-sentiment-aggregator-lxc.py (new)
 - nifi-sentiment-ingest.py
- **Installation:** folder with a docker-compose file to deploy an Apache NiFi instance.
- **Microservice:** Is still under construction.
- **Scripts:** three python files to export/import/execute an Apache NiFi workflow, and one python file to set the Apache NiFi Registry.
 - nifi-execute-flow.py
 - nifi-export-flow.py
 - nifi-import-flow.py
 - nifi-add-registry.py
- **Templates:** the exported version of the two Apache NiFi workflows that represent the two functions described in the component.
 - nipyapi-sentiment-aggregator-lxc-flow.json (new)
 - nipyapi-sentiment-ingest-flow.json

3.1.5 Social Dynamics & Behavioural Data Analytics

The code for the current Politika prototype resides in epinoetic.org/Politika/politika_demo_v2.tar.gz

3.1.6 Operational Data Repository

The source code of the operational datastore is based on the background technology that LXS is bringing to the project and is therefore proprietary. Therefore, the source code for this component cannot be provided to the consortium. Instead, LXS provides precompiled and pre-packaged binaries that can be used instead, containing all functionality developed so far. The binaries are accessible to the members of the consortium and have been uploaded in the private GitLab repository that can be found at: https://registry.grid.ece.ntua.gr/pavlos_LXS/policy-store

The GitLab repository additionally contains scripting files that allow the creation of a docker image that contains the LXS datastore distribution, so that the application developer or data scientist can run it locally for testing/experimentation purposes. This docker image is also being used by the Kubernetes cluster in order to deploy the data repository to be used by the integrated PolicyCLOUD solution.

3.2 Exploitation

This section provides information about where components are deployed and how they can be accessed and run.

3.2.1 DAA API Gateway

Setup of DAA prototype environment:

1. Install Kubernetes cluster ¹³
2. Install OpenWhisk and Kafka on the k8s cluster ¹⁴
3. Follow LeanXcale installation in section 3.2.6, run the docker image as `docker run -d -p 1529:1529 --name datastore policy-store:latest`
4. Setup OpenWhisk environment:
 - 4.1. Git clone DAA code from Section 3.1.1
 - 4.2. Create namespace policycloud
 - 4.3. Create package daa
 - 4.4. Create the web actions components for data source and analytic functions:
 - 4.4.1. `wsk package update daa -p brokers '["10.111.3.60:9092"]' -p accessToken 897df16803b16d34a750c79fde5d120d2dff31d5 -p repo policycloud -p branch master -p owner OSHRITF (Supply the gitlab credentials to the package creation)`
 - 4.4.2. to pull node-modules run: `npm install`
 - 4.4.3. create analytic function web action zip file: `zip -r action.zip`
 - 4.4.4. `wsk action update /policycloud/daa/analytic-function ./analytic-function/action.zip --kind nodejs:10 -a provide-api-key true --web true`
 - 4.4.5. create data sources web action file: `zip -r action.zip`
 - 4.4.6. `wsk action update /policycloud/daa/datasource ./datasource/action.zip --kind nodejs:10 -a provide-api-key true --web true`

Python and Java reference sample functions can be found in the repository (src/main), source code and packaged for use in OpenWhisk. Those are provided as examples to assist analytic owners to write their ingest/analytic functions.

3.2.2 Enhanced Interoperability & Data Cleaning

3.2.2.1 DATA CLEANING COMPONENT

The Data Cleaning software prototype is a Python project. As a result, to be able to run the prototype manually, Python should be properly preinstalled and preconfigured on the system and PYTHONPATH should include all the modules of the Data Cleaner prototype. In order to facilitate the exploitation process, the source code has to be downloaded from the repository, and then has to be opened as a Python project in the preferred IDE. On top of that, since various of the used modules are not pre-installed, the user has to manually install them. To do so, the user has to use the de facto standard

¹³ <https://kubernetes.io/docs/tasks/tools/>

¹⁴ <https://github.com/apache/openwhisk-deploy-kube>

package-management system used to install and manage software packages written in Python (pip). In that case, the user has to run a cmd.exe terminal with the current Python environment, and write the following commands:

Installing pandas-schema

```
$ pip install pandas-schema
```

Installing flask

```
$ pip install flask
```

Installing library for language detection

```
$ pip install langdetect
```

Installing library for emojis

```
$ pip install emoji
```

Installing spacy tool for spanish language

```
$ python -m spacy download es_core_news_sm
```

Installing spacy tool for english language

```
$ python -m spacy download en_core_web_sm
```

Installing library for NLP processes

```
$ pip install nltk
```

As soon as this process gets complete, the user has to simply run the program in a development server, since it is the first version of the prototype, and visit the following URL in a web browser:

<http://127.0.0.1:5000/cleaning>

This will start the Data Cleaner prototype as a web application and the exposed external interface will be available at *localhost:5000*.

3.2.2.2 ENHANCED INTEROPERABILITY COMPONENT

As analyzed in the previous section several dependencies and tools must be fulfilled and installed in order the provided code to be executed. First, there are some prerequisites that need to be fulfilled in order the user to be able to execute the several NLP subtasks that are incorporated in this component. To this end, Python3 and pip installer [14] should be properly preinstalled and preconfigured on the system. Finally, availability of the Neo4j graph database is a prerequisite for the use of the Ontology Mapping subtask.

What is more, below there is a list of all the wanted tools and libraries and their installation guides.

Installing Neo4j

```
$ pip install neo4j
```

Installation of the neo4j package for the Python language in order to be able to perform queries and have data integration with the powerful Neo4j graph database.

Installing spaCy

SpaCy can easily being installed via a pip installer, which is utilized to install Python libraries, and the following statement:

```
$ pip install -U spacy
```

Otherwise, if Anaconda [13] tool is already installed in the machine the following command on the Anaconda prompt needs to be executed:

```
$ conda install -c conda-forge spacy
```

Once the spaCy has been downloaded and installed, the next step is to download the language model, which in this case is the English language model. The language model is utilized to perform a variety of NLP tasks, which were introduced in previous sections. To this end, the following command downloads the appropriate language model:

```
$ python -m spacy download en
```

Installing qwikidata

A Python package with tools that allow to integrate and interact the provided data with Wikidata. The package defines a set of classes that allow to represent Wikidata entities, which is being utilized by the Interoperability component in order to interlink recognized entities from raw texts with Wikidata entities with the ultimate goal to extract JSON URI annotated data. This specific tool can be executed only in machines and environments with installed Python 3.5 or newer versions. Moreover, this package incorporates SPARQL and gives the availability to the end user to utilize SPARQL queries.

The most recent version of this package can be installed by using pip installer, *\$ pip install qwikidata*

As soon as the above processes and installations get complete, the user has to simply run the program in a development server, and visit the following URL in a web browser:

<http://127.0.0.1:5000/interoperability>

This will start the Enhanced Interoperability prototype as a web application and the exposed external interface will be available at *localhost:5000*.

3.2.3 Situational Knowledge Acquisition & Analysis

For this prototype, the functionalities described for this component have been deployed in a private environment. However, it can be replicated following the instructions and files provided in the git repository from Section 3.1.3.

3.2.4 Opinion Mining & Sentiment Analysis

The functionalities expected for this component will be deployed in a private environment. However, it can be replicated following the instructions and files that will be provided in the git repository.

3.2.5 Social Dynamics & Behavioural Data Analytics

Politika is currently deployed at the GRNet cloud. It can be accessed at: <http://epinoetic.org:4000>

The installation instructions that follow refer to a Linux machine and have been tested with the Ubuntu distribution.

- To install Erlang, Elixir, Phoenix and Postgres follow the instructions at:
 - <https://hexdocs.pm/phoenix/installation.html>
- Extract the politika_demo.zip file. A politika_demo directory will appear at the site of extraction.
- Open with a text editor (e.g. gedit) the politika_demo/config/config.exs file and update the following text section with the credentials for the Postgres installation in your system assuming that Postgres runs locally using port 5432 (otherwise update the fields hostname: and port: accordingly):
 - config :politika, Politika.Repo,
 - database: "politika",
 - username: "XXXXXXXX",
 - password: "XXXXXXXX",
 - hostname: "localhost",
 - port: "5432"
- Open a terminal window go to the politika_demo directory and setup the database from within ecto by typing:
 - mix ecto.create
 - mix ecto.migrate
- Run the politika system by typing in the politika_demo directory:
 - mix phx.server
- The system will start running in your machine at port 4000. For example, you can access Politika by typing the following address in your browser:
 - <http://<Your IP address>:4000>

3.2.6 Operational Data Repository

In order to use the operational data repository, it is highly recommended to make use of a docker container. Firstly, the user needs to download the current version of the binaries by executing the following:

```
git clone https://registry.grid.ece.ntua.gr/pavlos_LXS/policy-store
```

Then assuming the docker is already installed in the host machine, he or she needs to create the corresponding docker image, by executing the following:

```
docker build -t policy-store .
```

After building the image, he or she can check that it is available in the host machine's docker catalogue. To start the container, he or she would need to execute the following:

```
docker run -d -p 2181:2181 -p 1529:1529 --name datastore --env KVPEXTERNALIP='datastore!9800' policy-store {image_id}
```

This will create a single container running in the background where the data store will be installed and start in an all-in-one fashion. It is important to notice the `-p 1529:1529` parameter that exposes the 1529 port to the host machine, so that it can be reachable by another process outside of the container that has access to the network of the host machine.

To connect to the container via the console, she should execute the following:

```
docker exec -it policy-store bash
```

Then, he or she should be able to verify that all components are up and running, by executing the following:

```
${BASEDIR}/LX-BIN/bin/lxConsole 3
```

4. Conclusion

We provided in this deliverable a description of the software demonstration for the components which relate to the Integrated Data Acquisition and Analytics (DAA) Layer. They provide the analytical capabilities of the PolicyCLOUD platform. In October 2021 (M22) the provided demonstrators are integrated for 2 end-to-end scenarios. The integration for all the use cases will be provided in the next SW demonstrator deliverable: D4.6 Reusable Model & Analytical Tools: Software Prototype 3 due in October 2022.

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